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**Update of Report (D1.2) from user survey
with personas canvas**

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¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

- R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

- PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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List of Abbreviations and definitions

The abbreviations and definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary³.

Key definitions for this document:

Name	Definition
Information collection	Systematic gathering of data from various sources, such as surveys, interviews, observations, or existing databases. Information collection focuses on obtaining the necessary information required to address a research question, study, or analysis.
Data collection	Process of gathering or acquiring data from various sources for a specific purpose.
Data ingestion	Process of uploading or importing collected data into a data storage or processing system for further analysis or utilisation.
Data capture	Process of extracting information from any type of document or email and converting it into a format readable by a computer.

³ <https://www.aidava.eu/helpdesk/glossary>

Executive summary

This Deliverable D1.8 provides an update of Deliverable D1.2 and supersedes D1.2. While Deliverable D1.2 described the results of the work of the first phase of Task 1.2 of the AIDAVA project, Deliverable D1.8 completes this by adding the results of the work of the second phase of Task 1.2.

The AIDAVA project's Task 1.2 (T1.2) aimed to better understand the different user groups of the AIDAVA "AI-powered data curation and publishing virtual assistant" by involving two patient organisations, hospitals and health data intermediaries (HDIs). Also, T1.2 assessed patients' and citizens' interest and willingness to control and curate their personal health data.

In the first phase of Task 1.2, the project team developed, based on 39 in-depth interviews, 8 personas consisting of 2 patient personas, 2 data user personas, 2 data curator personas, and 2 third-party app developer personas. Foundation documents and persona canvases were created for each persona. Additionally, a survey was conducted with 250 participants to determine the general willingness of citizens to use a virtual assistant and what functionalities they would like the AIDAVA virtual assistant to have.

In the second phase of Task 1.2, the project team collected and analysed the findings and lessons learnt from the AIDAVA G1 prototype assessment study in the three test sites to identify all aspects of relevance for the update of the AIDAVA personas. The update of the AIDAVA personas according to the insights gained from the AIDAVA G1 prototype assessment study resulted in **nine** personas: One additional patient persona was elaborated to represent those, who are working with AIDAVA (only) on a smartphone. Further major updates of the patient personas concerned the patients' approaches for uploading documents to AIDAVA through the Health Data Intermediary and the patients' strategies for overcoming problems when using AIDAVA. Major updates of the data curator personas were related to their skills, motivation and challenges with respect to the job of an AIDAVA data curator. Only minor adjustments were needed for data user and third-party app developer personas. Additionally, to update the results regarding the general willingness of citizens to use a virtual assistant for automatic data curation, the survey was re-run to obtain the opinion of a broader group of respondents. The survey results of Phase 2 were strikingly consistent with the results of Phase 1, indicating that the trends collected are representative even with a small survey (± 250 people).

This information will be used to support the user-centred development of an AI-based data curation and publishing assistant. The personas will help developers empathise with different user groups, leading to more user-centric decisions. It will also serve as the foundation of the explainability and feedback layer for the user interface for patients - based on user profiles gathered when the user starts using the system for the first time. The personas will complement the business requirements specified in Task 1.3, and the user profiles can be based on the main characteristics of the personas.

1 Introduction

This deliverable is the result of the work conducted during Task 1.2 (user survey and definition of types of personas) in Work Package 1 of the AIDAVA project. Task 1.2 of the AIDAVA project was split into two phases: Phase 1 run from December 2022-April 2023, and Phase 2 was originally planned to run from July to August 2024 but was extended to December 2024 in order to be able to consider the findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study in the three AIDAVA test sites.

This Deliverable D1.8 is an update of Deliverable D1.2. While Deliverable D1.2 described the results of the work during the first phase of Task 1.2, this Deliverable D1.8 completes it by adding also the work conducted during the second phase of Task 1.2.

1.1 Problem to be solved and aim of Task 1.2

To achieve user-centric design and development of the AIDAVA prototype, it is crucial to develop a clear understanding of the (potential) future users, their framework conditions, interests, needs and expectations. For the AIDAVA prototype virtual assistant, four groups of potential users were identified:

1. Patients as the end users for AIDAVA who will curate their own data are one of the main user groups.
2. Expert data curators as hospital staff with medical knowledge/know-how in the healthcare field and with computer/data literacy who help patients to curate their data within AIDAVA; they will benefit from using AIDAVA in their everyday work if AIDAVA reduces their workload when curating patients' data.
3. Data-users in medical or research facilities who use patients' data to do their everyday tasks in the field of medicine and/or research.
4. Third party app developers who develop applications which utilise AIDAVA's APIs (application programming interfaces)⁴ either to provide health data to AIDAVA or to extract and reuse curated health data from AIDAVA.

The aim of Task 1.2 in the AIDAVA project was to enable broader participation across patient associations, hospitals and Health Data Intermediaries (HDIs) to better understand these different user groups. Furthermore, Task 1.2 also covered the assessment of patients'/citizens' interest and willingness to control and curate their personal health data.

The two main goals of Phase 1 of Task 1.2 were:

- Creating user personas (i.e. archetypical user descriptions) for the AIDAVA "AI-powered data curation and publishing virtual assistant" as a basis for following human-centred design principles in the development of the AIDAVA prototype.
- Assessing - through a mix of literature survey, online survey, and direct interviews - patients'/citizens' interest and willingness to control and curate their data.

⁴ In the context of the prototype to be delivered during the project, all integration will be done through existing APIs and/or through asynchronous data transfer based on predefined data transfer specification to minimise disruption with productive systems. The full product is however expected to develop the relevant APIs.

The goals of Phase 2 of Task 1.2 were:

- Updating the user personas for the AIDAVA “AI-powered data curation and publishing virtual assistant” by incorporating findings and lessons learnt from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study
- Updating the assessment of patients/citizens interest and willingness to control and curate their health data

1.2 About this Deliverable D1.8

This Deliverable D1.8 is an update of Deliverable D1.2. It adds the activities and results of the work conducted in Phase 2 of Task 1.2 to Deliverable D1.2 to provide a complete overview of Task 1.2.

The work in Phase 2 of Task 1.2 is specifically related to the following parts of this deliverable D1.8:

- A detailed description of activities undertaken in Phase 2 of Task 1.2 can be found in Subsection 2.2 of this deliverable.
- The results of the re-run of the citizens’ survey in Phase 2 of Task 1.2 are presented aside the results of the citizens’ survey conducted in Phase 1 of Task 1.2 in Subsection 3.1 of this deliverable.
- Relevant findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study and resulting updates of the personas’ foundations as well as personas’ visualisation canvas are included in Subsection 3.2 of this deliverable.
- Section 4 includes the summary of the results of all activities, for both phases of Task 1.2

2 Description of activities

To achieve the aims of Task 1.2, the **first phase of T1.2** was dedicated to conducting in-depth interviews with representatives of the potential AIDAVA user groups, conducting an online survey, developing personas and deriving the content of user profiles. For the user survey, a web-based questionnaire and targeted interviews were used to better capture from the point of view of (potential) future AIDAVA users any important data curation & publishing aspect that may not have been included in existing literature and other projects. The aim was to enable the participation of a large number of patients, including members of patient associations and citizens working with HDIs. The survey also included clinical staff who currently maintain registries. During the first phase of T1.2, for the different types of user groups of AIDAVA personas were created, which highlighted important factors related to the user's willingness to curate their data and which type of interaction and recommendations they expect to have with a virtual assistant.

The **second phase of T1.2** was dedicated to update the findings from Phase 1. Specifically, the relevant findings from the AIDAVA G1 prototype assessment study were collected and analysed and the AIDAVA personas were updated accordingly. Furthermore, the questionnaire, which was used in Phase 1 of T1.2 to get insights into patients/citizens interest and willingness to control and curate their health data, was slightly modified and the survey re-run to obtain input from a broader range of respondents.

All these activities are described in detail in the following subsections.

2.1 Activities in the first phase of Task 1.2

2.1.1 In-depth interviews with potential AIDAVA users

The aim of the user interviews was to collect input from the previously described potential user groups of the AIDAVA prototype. The results of the interviews help to follow human-centred design principles and consider the users' needs, abilities, skills, constraints and preferences during the design and development of the AIDAVA system.

The interview results form the basis for the development of archetypical users, so-called personas. Personas is a method well-known in the human-computer interaction field [1]. It was introduced in this project to help designers and developers focus on the needs and goals of the target users throughout the product development process. These personas will form the basis for elaborating user profiles.

Specifically, this interview helped to better understand:

- Attitudes, goals, motivations, frustrations, challenges and pain points
- Aptitudes, competencies, knowledge, skills and experience
- Personal/work context and framework conditions
- Interest and willingness to control and curate health data
- Motivations to make health data accessible and available for research
- Vision of an “ideal” data curation and publishing tool

In order to conduct the interviews in the same way among all participants, guidelines were created for the interviewers to follow while preparing and conducting the interviews. The guidelines included the

selection criteria for interviewees, a reminder to collect a signed informed consent from the participants before starting (template also provided by the project team), a description of the aims of the interview and important notes to bear in mind while conducting the interviews. The guidelines also described how to consolidate and present the results.

The interviews were conducted in English or local language, depending on the interview partners. Each of the interviews took around 40-60 minutes and open-ended questions were used to collect answers to motivate the interview partners to tell their story. Whenever possible, 2 people conducted the interview where one asked the questions and interacted with the interviewee, while the other observed and took notes.

In total, 39 interviews were conducted: 4 with third party app developers, 9 with data curators, 12 with data users and 14 with patients.

The results of the interviews were transcribed and those that were not conducted in English were subsequently translated. All the results were anonymised and checked to ensure that there was no identifiable information. The interviewees were given their final transcript for review and approval before translating and uploading it to project files.

2.1.2 Online survey

The purpose of the survey was:

- to find out the approach of citizens regarding their personal health data;
- to discover the attitude and expectations towards future usage of an automatic data curation tool such as AIDAVA.

The survey was created in REDCap ("Research Electronic Data Capture")⁵, a secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases, and it was distributed by the project partners via an online link. The survey was targeted at citizens who are potential users of the AIDAVA virtual assistant in the future. It was mainly meant to confirm with a wider audience, the input we received from the 8 "patient consultants"⁶ (4 cardiac patients selected by the European Heart Network (EHN) and 4 breast cancer patients selected by the European Coalition of Cancer Patients (ECPC)⁷) who helped us to define the patient perspective and requirements, during online calls and one face to face workshop in February 2023. The survey was shared therefore with the whole AIDAVA team, while the partners involved in T1.2 also shared it among their colleagues, family and friends. It was not intended to ask hospital patients in particular to fill in this survey nor to extend it broadly.

In order to cover all relevant topics, the questions were jointly developed by the partners in a shared document and then implemented in the survey in REDCap. For many of the questions, the response options consisted of selecting a numerical value from 0 (strongly disagree) to 10 (strongly agree). For example: The participants were asked to answer the question, "I am familiar with general medical

⁵ REDCap (Research Electronic Data Capture) <https://www.project-redcap.org/>

⁶ Patient consultants are patients selected by the patient organisations participating in the AIDAVA project based on predefined "inclusion/exclusion criteria". These patient consultants agreed to work throughout the project as consultant/advisors representing the views from patients. These patient consultants are not expected to share any personal data.

⁷ Note: In phase 2 of Task 1.2 ECPC was replaced by b!loba ad interim and then by DataForPatients.

terms.” using the scale from 0 to 10 to indicate how much they agreed or disagreed with this statement.

Care was taken to minimise open-ended questions in the survey (as opposed to the interviews where open-ended questions were favoured) to prevent participants from sharing personal information or sensitive data in the open text fields. Therefore, the focus was placed on questions that could be answered using buttons, sliders or checkboxes. To keep the survey compact and clear, some questions were only displayed if certain answer options were selected. This was done using branching logic in REDCap.

Every question except the first question (“I agree that my answers to this questionnaire are processed and analysed as described above.”), was defined as not mandatory.

Therefore, after agreeing that their answers can be processed and analysed, the participants were able to skip through the entire survey without filling out anything. This was done to motivate more people to participate in the survey, even if they do not want to answer specific questions.

Participants were not expected to spend more than 5-10 minutes to complete the survey.

To make it more convenient for participants and to motivate more people to complete the survey, it was translated into several languages. The contents of the final version of the survey were translated from English into German, Dutch and Estonian with the help of a translation table (in the form of an .xls file). The translated content was implemented in REDCap using multi-language management.

The survey was open for one month. After this time, the results of the 250 participants were analysed. The results are described in Section 3.1.

2.1.3 Development of personas

As already mentioned in Section 2.1.1, the *personas* method is well known in the field of human computer interaction (HCI) to support user-centred design. *Personas* are archetypes of users that make it easier for designers and developers to empathise with the users and to focus on the needs of the target user groups throughout the product development process.

For the development of personas, we followed the 5-steps approach suggested in *Personas for artificial intelligence (AI)* [2].

- Step 1 - identify user groups
- Step 2 - collect information about users
- Step 3 - consolidate and analyse information
- Step 4 - create personas' foundation
- Step 5 - visualise personas

Step 1. Identify user groups

In a first step - as described in Section 1.1 - four groups of people who would interact with a future AIDAVA system, were identified as potential future users.

Step 2. Collect information about users

In a second step, in-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted to collect information about these potential AIDAVA users, as described in detail in Section 2.1.1 of this document. The results of these interviews formed the basis for the development of personas.

Step 3. Consolidation and analysis of the interview results

The aim of Step 3 in the development process of personas was threefold: a) to get an overview of the information collected, b) to distil the important findings from the collected information, and c) to decide which personas to develop.

To get an overview of the information collected, it is important to gather all relevant information in one place. To achieve this, all narrative texts resulting from the interviews were copied into a single spreadsheet for each user group and structured by the interview questions and topics.

Figure 1. All interview results of a user-group were gathered in a spreadsheet structured by interview topics (source: MUG)

To distil from the collected information the important findings, i.e. those aspects which might be relevant for the usage of AIDAVA by the respective user group, we used the method of *affinity diagramming* [3]. First, the narrative texts of the interview results were split into single aspects. Then, all these single pieces of information were grouped in clusters based on their content relationships. Finally, for each of these clusters, a summary was formulated that concisely described the aspect(s) contained in that specific cluster.

	A	B	C
18 personal health data collection - what is collected	<p>I collect all documents from doctors/hospitals/lab tests</p> <p>[ECPC-1] Yes - I collect every document (blood test, treatment, diagnostic,...)</p> <p>[ECPC-2] Yes, I do collect everything - I collect: analysis, prescriptions, diagnostic material, radiology-images, letters from the doctor</p> <p>[ECPC-4] Yes, I collect all clinical data - I collect everything (x-rays, blood tests, doctor appointments,...)</p> <p>[ECPC-6] Yes, I collect all clinical data - I collect all clinical data that may be important for my condition</p> <p>[EHN-1] Yes collecting documents and data - All reports that are written after appointments, discharge summaries from hospitals,</p> <p>[EHN-4] Yes, collects medical records/documents</p> <p>[EHN-5] Yes collects documents/data/medical records related to personal health - Type of documents: she collects everything she can get and sorts them. She has documents/health records since birth. Most are from the hospital. She collects everything about her</p>	<p>I collect self-measured health-related data (in addition to clinical data)</p> <p>[ECPC-3] Yes - He collects blood pressure, imaging (TAC,CT,...), exercising, heart rate, steps counting...</p> <p>[ECPC-5] Yes, collect everything - Collects all personal health data possible; Mainly from an application from the hospital, but also from a phone health application (My health data). The hospital enforces keeping a health diary where I have to introduce personal health data collected by myself - I have to introduce all health data related to my condition</p> <p>[EHN-2] Yes, collects documents/data/medical records related to personal health (i.e. charts, graphs, notes,</p>	

Figure 2. Digest of clustered interview results created by the method of ‘affinity diagramming’ with a concise summary of each cluster’s content in red font

To decide which personas should be developed, a closer look was taken at the distilled findings to see if there were observable groupings across the interviewees’ answers for some aspects. For each of those aspects, where it became apparent that the interviewees representing a user group clustered into subgroups, it was reflected whether that specific aspect might have an influence on the usage of the AIDAVA prototype. For all aspects, which were believed to probably have an influence on the usage of the AIDAVA prototype, it was taken care that the specific parameter values found in the subgroups of the interviewees are covered by personas.

Step 4. Creation of personas foundations

For each user group a personas’ foundation document was created. The persona’s foundation contains a complete list of all aspects derived from the interview results, which form the basis of a persona.

patient	patient persona 1	patient persona 2	common for all patient personas
age			40-60
self-description "patient"			severe disease (cancer, serious heart disease...)
self-description "private life"			working and active life active in patients' association
self-description "education & work"			working changed job/retired due to health problems
self-description "motivation (for personal health data curation)"			accuracy of health records is important to get the right picture across to doctors to ensure receiving appropriate care
computer usage	uses computer at home regularly	uses a tablet at home	
smartphone usage	uses smartphone regularly	only has an ordinary mobile phone (no smartphone)	
educational background	some work experience / self education in data		
computer or data science	analysis/programming education in digital technology / highschool in computer programming	no educational background related to computers or data science	
			concerned about data privacy (worries about threats of data leaks/viruses/hackers/online

Figure 3. Detail from the patient personas foundations document

Step 5. Visualisation of the personas

To make it easier for people to empathise with the user represented by a persona, it is helpful to make the fictional persona a tangible, realistic character. To achieve this, a persona is visualised in a 1-page layout, a so-called personas canvas, which includes a picture and name of the persona and a narrative text about the persona's interests, behavioural patterns and attitudes.

Most content of the personas canvas is based on the aspects included in the personas foundation. However, to make the persona more realistic, some fictional elements (e.g. a fictional picture, a fictional name, fictional hobbies, etc.) are added to the canvas. It is important that all these fictional elements are in line with the persona's characteristics as described in the persona's foundation so that the canvas conveys all key aspects from the personas foundation.

For the visualisation of the personas, we adapted a personas canvas template from *Personas for AI* [4], which is publicly available.

Figure 4. Personas Canvas Template [4]

Validation of the personas

Visualisations of personas bear the risk of reinforcing stereotypes instead of providing a realistic picture of the users. Therefore, it is strongly recommended to validate the personas' canvases by asking people from the respective user group whether they feel plausibly represented by those personas. To obtain feedback from potential future AIDAVA users, we shared the personas canvas sheets to the respective interview partners with whom we conducted the in-depth interviews. We asked these people to tell us, (1) whether they think these personas are realistic and (2) whether in their point of view, any important aspects are missing in these personas.

The user feedback from this step was taken into account in the final versions of the AIDAVA personas. For example, we set the computer literacy of one of the patient personas to a lower level in response to the feedback from interview partners representing the user group of patients, who stated that one of the patient personas should be representative for people who are not very versed with computers.

The results of the whole process of personas development are described in Section 3.2.

2.2 Activities in the second phase of Task 1.2

2.2.1 Collection and analysis of relevant findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study

Three main activities were conducted to identify findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study, which might be relevant for the update of the AIDAVA personas: insights from point of view of the study nurses were collected in a structured shared document, the feedback obtained from the participating patients via the study evaluation questionnaire was analysed, and related aspects from point of view of the expert curators were collected in a short questionnaire. These activities are described in detail in the following paragraphs.

Collection of findings from study nurses

A structured shared document was prepared in the AIDAVA GoogleDrive to collect the findings gained by the three AIDAVA test sites (MUG, NEMC, MUMC/Maastro) from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study. Since the study nurses are those who were in closest contact with the participating patients - and thus have gained the best insights into patient's AIDAVA- and health data-related attitudes, expectations, struggles and concerns - they were asked to provide in this document all findings and observations which could be relevant for the update of the patient personas. To ensure that all relevant topics were covered and to provide the study nurses with a guidance on organising their insights and findings, the shared document included the following sections⁸:

- Patients demographics
- Patients' smartphone/computer usage and interaction preferences
- Patients' approaches when uploading data/documents to the Health Data Intermediary (HDI)
- Patients' approaches when answering AIDAVA's questions
- Patients' strategies for overcoming problems when using AIDAVA
- Patients' main information needs and questions regarding AIDAVA
- Patients' current challenges & issues related to their health data
- Patients' attitudes towards engaging with curation of their own health data
- Patients' attitudes towards sharing their personal health data
- Patients' motivation for participating in the AIDAVA study
- Patients' attitudes (concerns & expectations) towards future usage of an 'AIDAVA product'
- Patients' perceived need and expected benefits of having curated personal health data
- Patients' perceived need and expected benefits of having control over their health data
- Other relevant observations and insights from AIDAVA G1 testing

Analysis of the feedback from participating patients

At the end of the AIDAVA G1 assessment study, the participating patients provided their feedback and filled in an evaluation questionnaire. Within Task 1.2, the REDCap exports including the answers of the participating patients in the three AIDAVA test sites were analysed to identify any feedback from the patients, which might be relevant for the update of the AIDAVA personas.

⁸ Refer to Deliverable D1.7 for a detailed description of all findings collected in the AIDAVA G1 evaluation study.

Thereby, a focus was put specifically on the patients' answers to the following digest of questions of the evaluation questionnaire⁹, as these might reveal interesting insights relevant for the update of the AIDAVA personas:

- I would recommend AIDAVA to my friend, colleague, or family member
- I am ready to work with AIDAVA when available on the market
- I understand the purpose of data curation
- I am ready to spend the needed time to ensure proper curation of my data
- This system will allow me to manage my health records better
- Please write down any suggestions you might have on how we could improve/make AIDAVA easier to use.

Collection of findings from expert curators

To collect information, which could be relevant for the update of the curator personas, a short questionnaire was set up in REDCap. It included the following questions, addressed to the expert curators who were involved in the AIDAVA G1 assessment study in the three AIDAVA text sites:

- In your opinion, which knowledge and skills are necessary to do the job of an AIDAVA expert curator?
- In your opinion, which personality traits are needed to do the job of an AIDAVA expert curator well?
- What do you especially like about the job of an AIDAVA expert curator?
- What are the main challenges in the job of an AIDAVA expert curator?
- If an “automatic health data cleaning machine” like AIDAVA existed in the future, expert curators would be needed to support patients. Would you be willing to act as an expert curator?
 - If respondents answered “No” a follow-up question was asked:
Why would you not want to act as an expert curator? What are your main concerns?
- From your point of view as an expert curator: What are the most important aspects and features of an “automatic health data cleaning tool”, so that it will be practically useful?
- Any other comments, experiences or insights you want to share with AIDAVA?

All expert curators, who were involved in the AIDAVA G1 assessment study in the three AIDAVA test sites, were asked to share their experiences and insights by filling in that questionnaire. This questionnaire was in English, but the respondents could answer in their native language, if they preferred.

2.2.2 Adaptation of the citizens' questionnaire and re-run of the citizens' survey

In the second phase of Task T1.2 the online citizens' survey, which was already conducted in the first phase of Task T1.2 was re-run. The main aim of the citizens survey in Phase 2 of T1.2 was to gain insights from a broader group of respondents regarding citizens' attitudes towards sharing their health data, using an automatic health data curation tool, and the main functionalities they would expect from such a tool.

To achieve this, the REDCap questionnaire developed in Phase 1 of T1.2 (see chapter 2.1.2 for details) was slightly modified and, by concentrating on the most important questions only, also substantially

⁹ For a detailed description of the complete results of the G1 evaluation refer to Deliverable D1.7.

shortened (from 71 to 40 answer-fields). The following questions were included in the adapted questionnaire:

General background:

- Age
- Background related to medicine/healthcare
- It is easy for me to understand the medical reports I receive from my doctors / hospitals

Approaches and attitudes regarding medical data:

- I would say I am a person with an active medical dossier (I need - or I needed - to visit a doctor frequently)
- I am interested to keep track of my medical history/records
- For me, it is difficult to keep track of my medical history/records
- I would like to have all my medical documents and data in one place
- I would like to have all my medical data in machine-readable format, so that I can easily share them with others
- I would like to have all my medical data in machine-readable format, so that I can use computer programs to manage my medical data and keep an overview more easily
- I would be willing to help with keeping my medical data correct and consistent
- For me, it is very important to have control over my medical data
- Do you collect documents/data about your personal health, such as vaccination certificates, medical reports, medicine prescriptions...?

Access to data/documents about your personal health

- Have you ever wanted to request - or requested - your medical data from the hospital?
- Have you ever wanted to request - or requested - your medical data from your doctor (GP)?
- I think the access to my medical data from a hospital is easy for me
- I think the access to my medical data from a doctor (GP) is easy for me

Sharing personal health data

- I would share my personal health data with
My doctor - My partner - My family - My caregiver - My insurance company - Others

Expectations and attitude towards “intelligent health data system”

- If there would be an “intelligent health data system” in the future, how would you rate the importance of the following functionalities of such a system:
 - The system shall provide search and query functionality, so that I can easily retrieve specific health data
 - The system shall support me in sharing my health data with medical doctors
 - The system shall help me finding patient similar to me and propose relevant self-help-groups
 - In a medical emergency, the system shall inform first responders about relevant aspects in my medical history
- If an ‘automatic health data cleaning machine’ existed in the future, would you use it?

The online survey was available from 24.10.2024 to 17.12.2024 in English, Dutch, Estonian and German language. It was distributed by AIDAVA project partners and members of the AIDAVA advisory boards to their network contacts.

3 Results

In the following subsections, we describe in detail the results of the activities in Task 1.2 of the AIDAVA project, covering first the survey results and afterwards, in Section 3.2, the personas.

3.1 Results of the citizens' survey

The primary goal of the citizens' survey in the second phase of T1.2 was to gather insights from a larger group of respondents about their attitudes towards sharing health data, using an automated health data curation tool, and the key functionalities they would expect from such a tool.

3.1.1 Result description

Both, in Phase 1 as well as in Phase 2, every question, except the first one, in the online survey was non-mandatory to answer. Therefore, the amount of answers for each question might be different.

In the following paragraphs the results of the survey conducted in Phase 1 of T1.2 and the results of the re-run (of a slightly modified version) of this survey in Phase 2 of T1.2 are presented next to each other for better comparability.

Number and age of survey respondents

In Phase 1, from the 250 participants who filled out the survey at least partly, we obtained about 180-220 responses per question.

In Phase 2, out of the 131 participants who at least partially completed the survey, we received approximately 116 responses per question.

In Phase 1, of all the participants who answered the respective question, almost 50% (108 out of 218) were between 18 and 40 years old, while only 11% (25) were over the age of 60 years.

In Phase 2, among all participants who answered the respective question, nearly 70% (69 out of 117) were between 18 and 40 years old, whereas only 11% (9 participants) were over 60 years old.

Share of respondents with medical education

Phase 1: Of the 216 participants that answered the question whether they have an educational background related to healthcare or medicine, 144 participants (66% of the total responses) do not have an educational background related to medicine or healthcare.

Phase 2: Of the 116 participants who answered the question about having an educational background in healthcare or medicine, 95 (82% of respondents) indicated they do not have such a background.

For both survey phases, this suggests a potential bias in the surveyed population, leaning toward individuals who may be better informed about health-related topics compared to the general population.

Share of respondents with active medical dossier

Figure 5: Results of the statement “I would say I am a person with an active medical dossier (I need(ed) to visit a doctor quite frequently).” across the two phases.

- Explanation:
 - The scale to answer this question goes from 0 (strongly disagree) to 10 (strongly agree). For getting a better picture, we grouped them to 0/1 (strongly disagree), 2/3/4 (disagree), 5 (neutral), 6/7/8 (agree) and 9/10 (strongly agree).
 - Phase 1: A total number of 198 participants answered this question. The number in the pie chart indicates the number of participants that chose the respective answer option.
 - Phase 2: A total of 100 participants answered this question. The numbers displayed in the pie chart represent the number of participants who selected each respective answer group.

- Key message: There is a strong consistency across the answers of participants in Phase 1 and Phase 2. The majority of respondents (phase 1: 73%, phase 2: 70%) disagree or strongly disagree with the statement that they are a person with an active medical dossier; while less than a quarter (phase 1: 18%, phase 2: 24%) have an active medical dossier. We can consequently consider that the majority of the population that answered the survey (in both phases) are citizens in reasonable health.

Respondents' ease of understanding medical reports

A bias in the surveyed population toward citizens better informed on health issues than the normal citizen population is also supported by the following pie charts, which show how easy the participants perceive it to understand reports they receive from their doctors / hospitals.

Figure 6: Results of the statement “It is easy for me to understand the medical reports I receive from my doctors/hospitals” across the 2 phases

- Explanation:
 - The scale to answer this question goes from 0 (strongly disagree) to 10 (strongly agree). For getting a better picture, we grouped them to 0/1 (strongly disagree), 2/3/4 (disagree), 5 (neutral), 6/7/8 (agree) and 9/10 (strongly agree).
 - Phase 1: A total number of 204 participants answered this question. The number in the pie chart indicates the number of participants that chose the respective answer option.
 - Phase 2: A total of 112 participants answered this question. The numbers shown in the pie chart represent the number of participants who selected each respective answer category.
- Key message: The majority of the participants (Phase 1: 60%, Phase 2: 58%) agrees or strongly agrees that they find it easy to understand the medical reports they receive from their doctors or hospitals. This seems to confirm the bias in the population who answered the survey toward citizens with some health literacy.

Respondents' approaches and attitudes regarding medical data

Figure 7. Results of specific statements related to “Approaches and attitudes regarding medical data”, in percentage across the two phases

- Explanation:
 - The scale to answer these questions goes from 0 (strongly disagree) to 10 (strongly agree). For getting a better picture, we grouped them to 0/1 (strongly disagree), 2/3/4 (disagree), 5 (neutral), 6/7/8 (agree) and 9/10 (strongly agree).
 - Phase 1: A total number of 198 participants answered the first and the third question. A total number of 202 participants answered the second question. The numbers in the bar diagram indicate the number of participants that chose the respective answer options.
 - Phase 2: A total of 104 participants answered the first and third questions, while 105 participants responded to the second question. The numbers shown in the bar chart represent the number of participants who selected each respective answer category.

- Key message: Numbers are very similar across the 2 phases. No clear conclusion can be made on whether the participants as a whole find it difficult to keep track of their medical history or records. However, the vast majority (Phase 1: over 91%, Phase 2: over 89%) of the participants agree or strongly agree that they would like to have all their medical documents or data in one place, while only a few (Phase 1: 4,4%, Phase 2: 5.7%) of the participants disagree or strongly disagree on that. Furthermore, the majority (Phase 1: more than 78%, Phase 2: more than

85%) of the participants agree or strongly agree that they would be willing to help to keep their medical data correct and consistent.

Participants very clearly agree on wanting to have all their medical documents and data in one place. Additionally, there is a clear willingness to help in keeping their medical data correct and consistent. Especially the results of the last question draw a very favourable picture for the usage of AIDAVA in the future.

Important functionalities of an “intelligent health data system”

Participants were also asked to rate the importance of various functionalities for a potential "intelligent health data system" in the future. The most definitive responses are summarised in the charts below.

Figure 8. Phase 1: Average results of specific statements in “How would you rate the importance of the following functionalities of such a system?” across the two phases

- Explanation: Scale to answer these questions from 0 (strongly disagree) to 10 (strongly agree).
- Key message: In both, Phase 1 and Phase 2, surveys we find similar results: Participants expressed the greatest interest in having the system inform first responders (i.e., treating physicians) about relevant aspects of their medical history during a medical emergency, as well as providing search and query functions and assisting in sharing health data with medical professionals. In contrast, most participants did not consider it important for the system to help them find similar patients or suggest relevant self-help groups.

This corresponds to the feedback we received from the patient consultants - supporting definition of patient related requirements for AIDAVA - that the first reason for them to use a tool like AIDAVA would be to ensure their treating physician has access to the correct information - anytime, anywhere.

Respondents' willingness to use an "automatic health data cleaning machine" in the future

Figure 9. Results of the question "If such an 'automatic health data cleaning machine' existed in the future, would you use it?" across the two phases

As shown in Figure 9, when participants were asked if they would use an "automatic health data cleaning machine" with the functionality of AIDAVA, the majority (Phase 1: 115 out of 194 (59%), Phase 2: 63 out of 100 (63%)) selected "Yes", and only few (phase 1: 13, phase 2: 5) selected "No".

Since such a slight majority (phase 1: 59%, phase 2: 63%) does not allow to make a valid conclusion, we decided to split the participants in two groups:

- Those respondents who disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement "I would say I am a person with an active medical dossier (I need(ed) to visit a doctor quite frequently)" (see Figure 5) - these respondents are summarised as "participants WITHOUT medical dossier" in the following paragraphs
- Those respondents who agreed or strongly agreed having an active medical dossier - these respondents are summarised as "participants WITH medical dossier" in the following paragraphs

Those participants (phase 1: n=7, phase 2: n=6) who filled out the question on whether they would use a tool like AIDAVA, but did not answer the question regarding the active medical dossier, are not included in the following pie charts.

As can be seen from Figure 10, the percentage of participants who would agree to use a tool like AIDAVA is strikingly different between the two respondent groups: a slight majority (Phase 1: 54% , Phase 2: 59%) for the participants WITHOUT medical dossier; a large majority (Phase 1: 81%, Phase 2: 71%) for the participants WITH medical dossier (and therefore people with active medical conditions). This nicely demonstrates that people with a real medical problem or a more complicated medical dossier would be more interested in a tool like AIDAVA.

Figure 10. Participants **WITHOUT** (left column) and **WITH** (right column) active medical dossier who agreed to potentially use AIDAVA - across the two phases

Expected benefits of using an “automatic health data cleaning machine” in the future

As can be seen from Figure 11, the main benefits people expect from using an ‘automatic health data cleaning machine’ are having all health data correct and consistent in one place for better medical treatment, especially in emergencies. This result was found in both, Phase 1 and Phase 2 surveys.

Figure 11. Results of the question “Why would you like to use an ‘automatic health data cleaning machine’? What benefits do you expect?” across the two phases

Concerns regarding usage of an “automatic health data cleaning machine” in the future

In the Phase 2 survey, those respondents, who stated “I do not know” (n=22) or “no” (n=5) to the question “If an ‘automatic health data cleaning machine’ existed in the future, would you use it?”, were asked to write down their concerns why they would not want to use such a tool.

As can be seen from Figure 12, their main concerns were related to data privacy and security as well as lack of information about how the ‘automatic health data cleaning machine’ works.

Figure 12. Results of the question “Why would you not want to use an ‘automatic health data cleaning machine’? What concerns do you have?”

3.1.2 Conclusions

In both phases, the population who answered the survey seems to be more representative of healthy citizens - with some level of health literacy - than patients with an active disorder (and active medical dossier). The majority of the survey respondents is interested in keeping their dossier in a central place (Phase 1: 91%, Phase 2: 89%), and to increase the quality of this dossier (Phase 1: 78%, Phase 2: 85%) - independently of the fact that they have an active medical dossier or not. The main reason for doing so is to ensure the treating physicians have access to the appropriate information, certainly in emergency situations. These findings align perfectly with the input we received from the 8 patient consultants, and the insights we have gained from the patients, who participated in the AIDAVA G1 assessment study.

For AIDAVA, it is interesting to mention that currently, only a slight majority of the survey respondents (Phase 1: 59%, Phase 2: 63%) would use a tool like AIDAVA to support them. When only considering the participants having an active medical dossier, this number increases substantially (Phase 1: 81%, Phase 2: 71%). It indicates that the survey respondents are more concerned about risks of such a system like security and reliability, when they are not active patients, therefore not having the need for a tool like AIDAVA. This means that AIDAVA would profit from ensuring high security and reliability of the system, and also from offering user training covering both data literacy as well as the risks and benefits of a system like AIDAVA.

3.2 Personas

In Phase 1 of Task T1.2, in total eight personas were developed across the four groups of people, who were identified as potential future AIDAVA users: patients, expert data curators, data users, and 3rd party app developers.

In Phase 2 of Task T1.2, these personas were updated according to the insights gained during the AIDAVA G1 prototype assessment study in the three AIDAVA test sites.

In the following subsections, the updated persona's foundation as well as the persona's visualisation is presented for each of these personas.

3.2.1. Updated patient personas

Relevant findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study

As described in detail in Section 2.2.1, insights from point of view of the study nurses were collected in a structured shared document and the feedback obtained directly from the participating patients via the study evaluation questionnaire was analysed in order to identify findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study, which might be relevant for the update of the AIDAVA personas.

The following table lists those findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study, which are relevant for the elaboration of AIDAVA patient personas, and indicates how these findings are considered in the update of the AIDAVA personas.

Findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study	Respective Update of patient personas
Age of the patients participating in the study: 35-67 years (BC patients), 39-71 years (CVD patients)	Adjust age range of patient personas
Medical literacy of the patients participating in the study: 73%: LOW (medical literacy score 0-20); 20%: MEDIUM (medical literacy score 21-29); 7% HIGH (medical literacy score 30-35)	Adjust scale of medical literacy to LOW-MEDIUM-HIGH
Digital literacy of the patients participating in the study: 36%: LOW (digital literacy score 0-15); 47%: MEDIUM (digital literacy score 16-24); 17% HIGH (digital literacy score 25-30)	Adjust scale of digital literacy to LOW-MEDIUM-HIGH

Findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study	Respective Update of patient personas
<p>Patients' smartphone/computer usage and interaction preferences with AIDAVA:</p> <p>MUG (Austria):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> BC patients used their smartphone to work with AIDAVA, because they are used to working with their smartphone in their daily digital routines (e.g. social media, online shopping, internet search, YouTube...). However, they found it cumbersome to read/correct texts on the small screen CVD patients preferred to work with AIDAVA on their laptop; smartphone mainly used for blood pressure measuring app; <p>NEMC (Estonia):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> BC + CVD patients preferred to use a computer to work with AIDAVA (only 2 BC patients used a smartphone) <p>Maastricht/MUMC (Netherlands):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Majority of patients used AIDAVA on their smartphone (only a few used AIDAVA on their laptop or tablet computer) A few (older) CVD patients needed help from family to work with AIDAVA 	<p>2 groups:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) work with AIDAVA on smartphone (only) 2) work with AIDAVA on laptop computer (only)
<p>Patients' approach when uploading data/documents to HDI:</p> <p>MUG (Austria):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> most patients took photos from paper documents with their smartphones for upload to MIDATA, because patients in Austria usually receive medical documents/reports in printed format via mail; Some patients downloaded pdf documents from ELGA (Austrian electronic health records platform), but many patients had no ID Austria (electronic signature) necessary for accessing ELGA <p>NEMC (Estonia):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All patients downloaded pdf files from the national health information system 	<p>2 groups:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) upload pictures taken from paper documents with smartphone 2) upload pdf files downloaded from national health data portal
<p>Patients' strategies for overcoming problems when using AIDAVA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Few patients (with higher digital literacy) first tried to solve the problem on their own Some patients reached out for clarification by phone or email; Some patients gave up when facing problems with the AIDAVA tool and waited for their next encounter with the study nurse. Especially people with low digital literacy request in-person support (e.g. from family members) if problems arise; 	<p>3 groups:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) trying themselves to solve problem 2) reaching out for remote help (e.g. call helpdesk) 3) asking for in-person help (e.g. family member)

Findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study	Respective Update of patient personas
<p>Patients' current challenges and issues related to their health data:</p> <p>MUG (Austria):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patients do have their health documents on paper stored in folders at home → issues with incomplete data and missing documents, issues with managing their documents; ● Patients have difficulties remembering certain dates of procedures and finding the related documents; ● Patients need to bring different sets of relevant documents to different physicians and must filter/sort their documents accordingly themselves <p>Maastro/MUMC (Netherlands):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patients need to repeat information a lot in clinical practice ● Information about medication is poorly updated in clinical practice ● Patients have a poor overview of where to find (all) their medical data <p>NEMC (Estonia):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patients have easy access to all their medical documents through the national Patient Portal → patients' report no challenges and issues related to their health data 	<p>Already covered by existing patient personas - no update needed</p>
<p>Patients' attitudes towards sharing their personal health data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Most patients are willing to share their health data for the purpose of quality of care - They want that all their treating physicians have got all data they need for making good decisions on their treatment ● Patients want to be informed about who has access to their data ● Some patients stated that they want that their personal data is used for research to contribute to progress in medicine so that it can "help our next generation" 	<p>Already covered by existing patient personas - no update needed</p>
<p>Patients' attitudes (concerns & expectations) towards future usage of an AIDAVA product:</p> <p>Patients are willing to use a future AIDAVA product</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● if the AI-tools work properly and the system is user-friendly with a very easy to read user-manual, and proper translated into local language ● If it is usable across countries to share your health data anywhere in the world (e.g. for showing the IPS in a foreign language to a doctor during holidays) ● If it provides good search functionality so that they can find documents easily ● If all hospitals and doctors will have access to their data and will use AIDAVA ● If their health data are kept secure 	<p>Already covered by existing patient personas - no update needed</p>
<p>Patients' perceived need and expected benefits of having curated personal health data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Most patients do not understand the need for curation and the benefits of curated data ● Main benefits patients expect from AIDAVA is that all their health data is collected in one place and can be easily accessed, and they can use and share their IPS abroad 	<p>Already covered by existing patient personas - no update needed</p>

Findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study	Respective Update of patient personas
Patients' perceived need and expected benefits of having control over their personal health data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients want that all their treating healthcare professionals should have access to their medical data automatically • Patients want to be able to share information themselves at convenience 	Already covered by existing patient personas - no update needed

Taking into account these findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study, the two existing patient personas (developed in Phase 1 of Task 1.2) were slightly updated and a third patient persona was developed. This is reflected in the updated foundation for AIDAVA patient personas.

Updated foundation for AIDAVA patient personas

All aspects mentioned in the following personas foundations table are based on the interview results (conducted in Phase 1 of Task T.2) and the findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study in the three AIDAVA sites (collected in Phase 2 of Task T1.2).

	patient persona 1	patient persona 2	patient persona 3	common for all patient personas
age				35-70
digital literacy	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	
medical literacy	HIGH	MEDIUM	LOW	
health condition				severe disease (cancer, serious heart disease...);
private life		active in patients' association		active life (hobbies...)
education & work	changed job due to health problems	working	working flexible hours	
motivation for personal health data curation				accuracy of health records is important to get the right picture across to doctors to ensure receiving appropriate care
computer usage	uses computer regularly, proficient computer user	uses a tablet at home	does not own a computer or tablet	
smartphone usage	uses smartphone regularly	only has an ordinary mobile phone (no smartphone)	uses smartphone regularly	

	patient persona 1	patient persona 2	patient persona 3	common for all patient personas
Interaction with AIDAVA	prefers to use a computer to work with AIDAVA	uses a tablet to work with AIDAVA	uses a smartphone to work with AIDAVA	
educational background computer or data science	education in digital technology	no educational background related to computers or data science	some education in digital technology (school/work experience or self-education)	
data rights and privacy aspects	likes to be the owner of their data and to know who holds what data about them/their family and what is happening with their data	data privacy is important - (concerned about threats of data leaks/viruses/hackers/online insecurity); the only people who should have their data are the medical staff and the people they consent to having their data	thinks that people should not be overly cautious with data privacy when it comes to sharing data for research, but see the huge benefit data can bring about	concerned about personal right to access own data; does not want their data to be used commercially without their knowledge and consent; data privacy is important, but having to give consent every time when you go to the doctor is cumbersome
reading manual for new device	usually dives right into when using a new device (reads manual only when encountering an issue - prefers visual instruction because reading is boring)	usually reads the manual carefully before using a new device		

	patient persona 1	patient persona 2	patient persona 3	common for all patient personas
feelings about getting a new device	finds changing to new devices exciting, loves new gadgets and likes exploring them	apprehensive to give up familiar device, but then happy to have new functions and possibilities		
level of specific medical knowledge regarding own disease	HIGH ('googles' and reads everything about their condition to better understand it)	MEDIUM (does not understand everything but has a good baseline knowledge; knows more than the general population)	MEDIUM	
level of familiarity with general medical terms	HIGH (knows many but not all medical terms)	MEDIUM (mostly familiar with terms regarding their own personal health condition)	LOW often does not fully understand the medical documents due to all the medical terminology and jargon used by the doctors	
educational background medicine / healthcare	educational background in medicine or healthcare	no educational background in medicine or healthcare	no educational background in medicine or healthcare	

	patient persona 1	patient persona 2	patient persona 3	common for all patient personas
personal health data collection - what is collected	collects in addition to clinical data also self-measured personal health data (blood pressure, physical activity, heart rate, steps counting, weight...) from hospital app & phone health-application	collects all medical documents related to their health condition (lab test results, treatment, diagnostic material, prescriptions, letters from doctors, imaging (radiology images, CT...), discharge summaries from hospitals...)	collects self-measured personal health data (on the smartphone)	
format of collected data	most health data are digital (pdf), but some on paper	receives only paper documents (and medical images on CD)	all health data digital (pdf), accessible in national health data portal	
approach for uploading data to AIDAVA via HDI	uploads pdf files and pictures taken (with smartphone) from paper documents	upload pictures taken (with tablet) from paper documents	uploads pdf files downloaded from national health data portal	
storage of collected data	stores digital health documents on computer at home; stores paper documents in folder/box and keeps scanned copy on computer; self-measured personal health-related data is kept in health app	stores paper documents in folder/box at home	no need to store medical data at home, as they are easily accessible at the national health data portal; self-measured health data are stored on the smartphone	

	patient persona 1	patient persona 2	patient persona 3	common for all patient personas
motivation for data collection	collects health data for themselves to better understand & monitor their condition	collects everything in paper format, because they can read it and like to insert comments on the side of the document on paper	wants to have a complete IPS usable across countries	collects health data to share it (with doctors, insurance...)
challenges and issues regarding health data collection	health data retrieval is not easy (no one-stop-shop for all medical records, difficult to retrieve data from the past, complicated to receive doctors' notes, lengthy and tedious formal consent procedure needed to get own health data from hospital, difficult to know whom to ask for the documents)	paper documents need a lot of space to store, are difficult to manage, and not environmentally friendly	there is no easy way for sharing personal health data across countries and languages; I do not understand the reports I get because of the medical jargon /terminology	I cannot see images/MRI scans at home since I do not have the necessary software to read these files; health information is often not complete (parts of information are forgotten to insert/upload and health information coming from other sources is not collected by the health personnel)
monitoring health-related parameters at home	regularly monitors health-related parameters at home (e.g. blood pressure, heart rate, physical activity, weight); shares data with doctor through app;	does not measure health-related parameters at home	measures health-related parameters at home only when feeling not ok and shares data (as pdf) with doctors only if something seems to be alarming	

	patient persona 1	patient persona 2	patient persona 3	common for all patient personas
using health/fitness app or device	uses a health app / fitness tracker device	does not use a fitness-tracker app or device	uses a device for measuring blood pressure, which is linked to an app on their smartphone	
sharing personal health data	would consent to share data for good research purpose;	would share data only for clinical purpose if benefit for their health - all relevant clinical staff should have their latest data, but this should be monitored so that people only access it when they need it	wants to share data for research as this can bring about benefits for future patients	must be fully transparent for which purpose data are used - would consent on a case-by-case basis; no commercial use; data shared for research should be anonymised; there must be consent and strict regulation
reasons for AIDAVA usage; expectations towards AIDAVA	would use AIDAVA to own and control their own health data; excited to have a digital system for collecting, managing and improving the use of their health data	would use AIDAVA if it is easy to use and if they can be sure that their data is stored in a safe place	would use AIDAVA to have a comprehensive IPS, which they can show to doctors when abroad	would use AIDAVA... ...to collect their health data from different sources easier and faster ...to have all their health data (from different sources) with them all the time ...to have a clear picture of their health ...to make their complete, correct health data accessible to doctors ...to curate their health data (fix errors, remove unnecessary data) ...as they hope that the system takes care of their health

	patient persona 1	patient persona 2	patient persona 3	common for all patient personas
strategies for overcoming problems when using AIDAVA	if encountering (technical) problems with AIDAVA, they would first try by themselves to overcome these problems	if encountering (technical) problems with AIDAVA, they need someone to help them (would first ask someone in the family for help...)	if encountering (technical) problems with AIDAVA, they would reach out for clarification by phone or email	

Additional aspects distilled from interview results (conducted in Phase 1 of Task 1.2), which are not covered by the current patient personas:

- user is not the patient, but a relative (e.g. parent of a child with severe (congenital) disease)
- all medical records are online accessible in electronic health system of local health maintenance organisation / health data intermediary → problems mentioned by the interviewees: nobody else than the patients themselves can access their medical records in their local health data account; there is no line of communication and access between hospitals and the health maintenance organisation or health data intermediary

Visualisations of the updated patient personas

Lena Lopes

Age: 48 * Education: business informatics, nursing

DIGITAL LITERACY
HIGH

MEDICAL LITERACY
HIGH

SKILLS & KNOWLEDGE

- healthcare
- sense of responsibility
- accuracy
- curious and eager to learn
- organisational skills

MOTIVATIONS

- helping people
- work is useful
- getting positive feedback
- nice colleagues

FRUSTRATIONS

- missing data in her health records
- administration & paper work
- no easy way for sharing personal health data

VALUES & ASPIRATIONS

- respect for other people
- doing her job well
- staying active
- enjoying life
- healthy lifestyle
- family & friends

PERSONALITY AND BEHAVIOUR

Her friends and family would describe Lena as an active, friendly and optimistic person. Lena is open-minded and curious and finds it always interesting to learn something new. She is quite tech-savvy and proficient with using computers and smartphones. When she gets a new device or application, she dives right in and is eager to try out all the new functionalities. If she encounters technical problems, she tries to fix these herself.

OCCUPATION

Lena was working as a business consultant for more than 10 years. However, after she was diagnosed with breast cancer, she could not do so much travelling and long hours anymore. Therefore, she decided to change the job. She went to nursing school and is now working as a study nurse at the oncology department of the hospital in her hometown.

ATTITUDE TOWARDS HEALTH DATA

For Lena it is very important to always have a good overview of her health condition. She uses the health app on her smartphone to regularly monitor parameters such as heart rate and physical activity, and she collects all medical reports and documents from doctors and hospitals. Lena gets most of these data in digital format, but some documents are still on paper. She stores all health-related documents at home on her computer and keeps the papers in a box.

Lena thinks it is not easy to collect all her health data, as there is no one-stop-shop for all medical records, and there is also no easy way of sharing health data between different hospitals and doctors or transferring personal health data to another country. Furthermore, Lena noticed that sometimes information is missing in her records, as data are forgotten to insert or not collected by the healthcare personnel.

ATTITUDE TOWARDS AIDAVA

Lena would prefer to work with AIDAVA on her laptop computer. She would use AIDAVA to collect her health data from different sources easier and finds it convenient that she can also upload photos taken from paper documents. Lena wants to have all her health-related data and documents at her disposal whenever she needs them. She hopes AIDAVA can support her with fixing errors in her health data and making her complete and correct health records accessible to doctors.

Lena thinks that data privacy is essential and her personal health data should not be used without her consent. She would be happy to give consent to sharing her health data for a good research purpose. However, it must be fully transparent what the data are used for and by whom, and ideally data shared for research should be anonymised.

Bart Bit

Age: 63 * Education: retail & sales

DIGITAL LITERACY
LOW

MEDICAL LITERACY
MEDIUM

SKILLS & KNOWLEDGE

- communication
- counselling
- accuracy
- organisational skills
- self-confidence
- sense of responsibility

MOTIVATIONS

- helping people
- love working with people
- getting positive feedback
- nice colleagues

FRUSTRATIONS

- missing data in health records
- apps not working as intended
- complicated interfaces
- no easy way for sharing personal health data

VALUES & ASPIRATIONS

- respect for other people
- sharing experience
- staying active
- enjoying life
- healthy lifestyle
- family & friends

PERSONALITY AND BEHAVIOUR
His friends and family would describe Bart as a communicative, friendly, helpful and self-confident person. He uses a computer at work, but at home, he finds it sufficient to have a tablet for finding information on the internet, online banking and maintaining contacts on social media. Bart is definitely no technophile, and quite apprehensive to give up a familiar device, when he should get a new one. When any of the apps on his tablet does not work as usual, he asks his son for help.

OCCUPATION
Bart is working as a shop assistant in a hardware store already for some decades. He likes his job as he loves to communicate with people and share his expertise and knowledge. In his leisure time, Bart is active in a self-help group for patients with cardiovascular disease. Over the years he has acquired a substantial medical knowledge in this field.

ATTITUDE TOWARDS HEALTH DATA
Bart has a serious heart disease and had already two heart attacks. So far, he spent a lot of time at hospitals and doctors and thus has got quite substantial medical records. Bart collects all documents related to his disease, such as lab reports, reports from doctors and hospital discharge summaries. He gets all these documents in paper format and stores them at home in plastic folders. Managing the bulk of paper documents is not easy as they need a lot of space.
However, Bart finds it important to have all his health documents in order, so that he can bring them with him when he visits a new doctor or hospital. Bart also wants to have all data at hand in case the insurance asks for it, and he finds it important that his wife can easily access all information in case she needs it for example in an emergency.

ATTITUDE TOWARDS AIDAVA
Bart would work with AIDAVA on his tablet, if the system would be easy to use and not too time-consuming. But most important for him is that he can be sure his data is stored in a safe place. Bart is worried about online security and the threats of data leaks and is concerned about the protection of his personal health data. Bart is convinced that data privacy is very important and access to patients' health data must be monitored and strictly regulated so that people only get these data when it is needed.
Bart thinks the only people who should have his personal health data are the medical staff and the people he consents to having his data. He would share his personal health data only for clinical purposes to benefit his health condition and would wish that all relevant clinical professionals do have his latest data.

Julia Janko

Age: 36 * Education: stylist

DIGITAL LITERACY
MEDIUM

MEDICAL LITERACY
LOW

SKILLS & KNOWLEDGE

- communication
- counselling
- accuracy
- organisational skills
- self-confidence
- artistry

MOTIVATIONS

- making people happy
- creative work
- getting positive feedback
- nice colleagues
- flexible work options

FRUSTRATIONS

- no easy way for sharing personal health data
- administration & paper work
- boring tasks
- having to repeat information over and over again

VALUES & ASPIRATIONS

- respect for other people
- family & friends
- staying active
- enjoying life
- exploring other countries and cultures

PERSONALITY AND BEHAVIOUR
Her friends and family would describe Julia as an active, friendly and optimistic person. Julia is open-minded, creative and curious. She loves talking with people, traveling and exploring foreign countries and cultures. After work, she often spends a lot of time on her smartphone checking social media to stay in touch with her friends and up-to-date regarding the latest trends in fashion and style.

OCCUPATION
Julia loves her job as a stylist, as it allows her to express her creativity and provides the opportunity to build personal connections with clients. She likes to make people happy and boost their confidence by enhancing their appearance. Since Julia has cardiomyopathy, she is also glad to have a workplace with flexible scheduling options where she can adjust hours to her condition and fit in the frequent visits to her doctor needed for check-ups and treatment.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS HEALTH DATA
Julia has quite a substantial medical dossier, but often does not fully understand the documents due to all the jargon and medical terminology used by the doctors.
Nevertheless, Julia is glad that she does not need to store or manage all these medical documents from clinics or doctors at home, as they are conveniently available on the national electronic health data portal. To keep track of her medical condition, Julia is regularly monitoring health-related parameters at home. The results of these measurements are stored in an app on her smartphone, so that she can show them to her doctor during her regular visits.
However, what frequently concerns Julia while traveling is the lack of an easy way to share her medical data across different countries and languages.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS AIDAVA
Julia would use AIDAVA on her smartphone since she does not have a computer and is accustomed to handling her daily digital tasks on her phone.
Julia hopes that AIDAVA can be used internationally, across different countries and languages. She would like all her medical data to be curated in AIDAVA, enabling her to generate a comprehensive International Patient Summary (IPS) that she can present to doctors while traveling abroad.
Julia wants to share her medical data for research, as she believes that people should not be overly cautious and should recognize the value of how helpful data can be.

3.2.2. Updated data user personas

There were no major updates of the AIDAVA data user personas needed in Phase 2 of Task 1.2, as the AIDAVA G1 assessment study brought about no new insights with respect to data users, which were not already covered by the existing AIDAVA data user personas. This was mainly due to the fact that the development of the AIDAVA data user personas in Phase 1 of Task 1.2 was already done in close cooperation with those clinicians and researchers who also participated in the AIDAVA G1 assessment study at the three test sites.

Updated foundation for data user personas

All aspects mentioned in the following personas foundations table are based on the interview results (conducted in Phase 1 of Task 1.2), and confirmed by the experience from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study in the three AIDAVA sites (in Phase 2 of Task 1.2).

In Phase 2 of Task 1.2 only minor updates to the data user personas were needed. Specifically, the ratings of 'computer literacy' and 'medical expertise' levels were shifted from a 10-point scale to a more coarse-grained scale of LOW-MEDIUM-HIGH for 'digital literacy' and 'medical literacy', which better corresponds to the planned adaptation of the AIDAVA G2 prototype to the users' digital and medical literacy levels.

The following table shows the updated foundations for the two AIDAVA data user personas.

	data-user persona 1 ("researcher")	data-user persona 2 ("medical doctor")
age	35-60	35-60
digital literacy	HIGH self-assessment of computer-user skills 8-10; educational background in data science or acquainted knowledge in course of work and attended training courses	MEDIUM self-assessment of computer-user skills 4-6; no education in computer/data science; can manage everything work-related / everyday work is not a problem / works quite proficiently with programs they often use.
medical literacy	LOW familiarity with medical terms: 5; no medical education; when they need medical terms, they know where to look them up; acquired knowledge of medical terms during career.	HIGH familiarity with medical terms: 10; education: medical doctor; you cannot know everything and medical terminology also changes over time.
self-description	friendly, likeable, eloquent, always good mood, happy, optimistic, enthusiastic, hardworking, decision maker, straight forward, honest, uncomplicated, rather precise, careful, often very indecisive; parent	hardworking, conscientious, precise, quick, stubborn, relatively good stress tolerance in working under pressure, experienced, very calm person, likes chocolate very much.
attitude towards data protection and privacy (at	data protection and data privacy are very important especially when it comes to personal health data, but sometimes it is bothersome as it	data protection and data privacy are very important especially when it comes to personal health data, but sometimes it is a complex issue and an ethical dilemma (e.g.

	data-user persona 1 ("researcher")	data-user persona 2 ("medical doctor")
work)	hinders them in many surveys and research projects.	when inadvertently opening the wrong person's records or when discussing patient-related matters with another doctor and there's another person in the room); also in personal life they think about data protection rules and data protection.
attitude towards new technologies; feelings when getting a new smartphone	usually not reading user manuals, trying out new stuff on a trial-and-error basis, expect new devices to be self-explanatory and intuitive to use; trusts their experience on technology; if they get a new device, they are excited and eager to explore the new functionalities;	usually reads user manuals, but prefers that someone shows how it works (that's always easier); getting new technology is not a big thrill, they are not the kind of person to immediately buy a new thing and start researching on their own how to use it; usually choosing the same brand that they had before when needing to get a new device (- these devices are usually similar and this facilitates getting acquainted to handle the new one).
job / tasks	working in research projects in the medical field; initiating clinical studies and medical research projects.	medical doctor in a hospital (diagnostics, patient treatment); pathologist (histopathology diagnostics).
important skills for the job	computer & data-science related skills (basic SQL knowledge and data understanding; ability and willingness to learn dealing with hospital information system, specific databases, ETL and evaluation tools); communication and social skills (ability to communicate with professionals in different languages, coordinate and integrate different experts); management & research skills (keeping an overall picture and avoid getting lost in details, project management, problem solving, read & write scientific articles and conduct research).	medical knowledge; basic computer user skills, and willingness to keep learning different information systems as these are constantly being updated; communication and social skills (ability to communicate with different types of people, making things understandable to people with different levels of education, day-to-day interaction with patients and colleagues, psychological knowledge).

	data-user persona 1 ("researcher")	data-user persona 2 ("medical doctor")
personality traits for the job	self-motivation, focus, persistence acting self-reliant and autonomous calm, patience, excellent self-control interest in innovation, desire to develop, innovative, creative, curious, open to teamwork, collaboration.	empathy, being considerate of others and not too self-centred, friendly, ability to accept different opinions and tolerate various behaviours and situations; resilience to stress, stable nervous system, able to work under pressure; calm, patience, excellent self-control; accuracy, conscientiousness; being smart, speed in thinking and acting, analytical thinking; interest in innovation, desire to develop, innovative, creative, curious, teamwork, collaboration.
motivations / pleasure in job	successful completion of a task; getting positive feedback; freedom, independence, creativity; passion about future research, curiosity job is not boring - different things to do, opportunity for constant development, difficult and interesting cases (solving problems); work is useful, beneficial and valuable (opportunity to help people with their skills, and bring in / put into practice good ideas); good team and working atmosphere (respect and appreciation for colleagues and their work).	physical work/hands-on approach in the operating room; job is not boring - there are always different things to do, opportunity for continuous development, difficult and interesting cases; work is useful, beneficial and valuable (opportunity to help people with their skills, and bring in / put into practice good ideas); good team and working atmosphere (respect and appreciation for colleagues and their work).
challenges / frustrations in job	missing data and not reliable data (often documentation is poor and it is unclear whether data items are up-to-date); having to work with and depend on non-collaborative people; funding politics; administration and paperwork.	work overload and shortage of support staff - need to do a lot of extra hours. administration and paperwork; need to keep up with fast changes but no time for learning new things; lack of mental rewards.
purpose of health data retrieval	retrieves (many) patients' health data for research projects and clinical studies (needs to find all patients that fulfil specific inclusion and exclusion criteria).	retrieves a specific patient's health data for diagnostics and treatment of this patient (needs to get an overview of the patient's previous medical history).

	data-user persona 1 ("researcher")	data-user persona 2 ("medical doctor")
current procedure for access to health data of patients	access to patients' data for research purposes always needs the approval of the ethics committee and is not possible without a project.	to access a patients' health records authentication is required; access to patients' data is logged in the system (doctors should look only at "their" patient's data, whom they are treating).
current procedure for health data retrieval	retrieves data via SQL queries from the hospital archive system, or specifies which data are needed and asks a specific department at the university (data clearing site) to retrieve these data from hospital information system; researchers are relieved from responsibility for identifiable patient data since they get pseudonymised data from data-clearing site; data cleaning and pre-processing for research is a lot of manual work.	goes through the health record documents of the patient in the hospital information system and finds the necessary information in heterogeneous data (including also a lot of unstructured data such as narrative report texts).
current challenges in data retrieval	bad / unclear data quality (you don't know if that is the latest status for a specific entry/document in the system); analysing unstructured data and narrative texts (which often include words like "rather" and "probably"); currently no structured data entry into the hospital information system, no structured reports; no access to external patient data (e.g. from GP or from other (private) clinics); missing and incomplete data, due to mistakes in data retrieval process (not all available data from system retrieved) or when data was not entered into the system (someone forgot to input this information, or this information is not recorded - there is no field for that information in the system).	always needs to justify why they have looked at someone's data (if someone asks long time after it has happened they may not even remember the reason anymore); sometimes they cannot find the needed data/information (e.g. if layout of the digital system has changed); difficult to find information in long medical records (some people's medical history is many pages long and going through them takes time...); always feels that they are missing some medical data; lack of data (e.g. if someone has forgotten to input information on a medical test conducted for a patient) affects their work, wastes time and may lead to repetitive tests and procedures; missing and incomplete data, due to mistakes in data retrieval process or when data was not entered into the system (someone forgot to input this information, or this information is not recorded).

	data-user persona 1 ("researcher")	data-user persona 2 ("medical doctor")
attitudes and expectations towards automatic health data curation	would use such a tool for patient recruitment in clinical studies or for finding patients who fulfil specific inclusion and exclusion criteria for research projects.	such a tool should help with identifying important parts of information in a patient's medical records; such a tool should extract information from report texts and fill in forms automatically (e.g. order forms for analyses or concilium).
to be useful, such a system must...	... be safe and secure; be user friendly, convenient/easy to use; be easily accessible & easy to configure; be accurate; be interoperable; be usable for analysis of different data sources; recognise automatically if something is wrong; check data quality automatically; deliver the needed data in perfect quality; be up-to-date and fast; be reliable (provide reliable data).	... provide a good overview of the medical record (show only important things); provide data in such a way that they can be easily processed; be up-to-date and fast; be user friendly, convenient/easy to use; be reliable (provide reliable data).
trust in such an AI-based tool	wants to be able to understand why the tool found these patients/data – the tool should show this information; would not trust in tool 100% as they've already seen AI-tools making mistakes	if the company says this works, then they do not check; from this tool they would expect to get all data - so they would only make some random sample checks

Visualisations of the data user personas

Igor Ilia, Researcher

Age: 45 * **Education:** Study of Physics

DIGITAL LITERACY
HIGH

MEDICAL LITERACY
MEDIUM

SKILLS & KNOWLEDGE

- basic SQL knowledge
- data understanding
- persistence
- creativity
- communication
- project management
- keep focus
- accuracy

MOTIVATIONS

- solving interesting problems
- job is not boring
- successfully completing tasks
- work is useful
- getting positive feedback
- nice colleagues

FRUSTRATIONS

- missing data
- not reliable data
- work with non-collaborative people
- administration & paper work
- lack of funding

VALUES & ASPIRATIONS

- interest in innovation
- respect for other's work
- good working atmosphere
- passion for research

PERSONALITY AND BEHAVIOUR

His friends and family would describe Igor as friendly, uncomplicated and optimistic person. Igor loves to solve tricky puzzles. In the evening, when his two children are in bed, he enjoys to fully concentrate on these brainteasers. Solving logic problems has been one of his hobbies since his childhood. Igor is also passionate about technology and innovations and likes to discuss new trends and development opportunities with colleagues. When he gets a new device, he can't wait to try out all these novel functions. He always explores new gadgets and apps on a trial-and-error basis as he trusts his experience and expects new devices and software applications to be intuitive to use.

OCCUPATION

Igor works in research projects in the medical field for over 15 years. As a senior researcher at a medical university Igor is responsible for project acquisition and development. For many of his research projects it is essential to get data of patients who fulfil specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Thus, after obtaining approval by the ethics committee, Igor and his colleagues query the hospital archives and information systems to retrieve patients' data for their research. However, there is a lot of unstructured data in the system and extracting information from narrative texts of medical reports is quite a bit of manual work, error prone and very time consuming. Igor's main concerns are incomplete and missing data. He often worries about the quality of the data and whether he could retrieve all relevant information from the system.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS DATA PRIVACY

Igor is convinced that data protection and privacy are essential when dealing with personal health data, but sometimes these issues seem to hinder research work. Therefore, Igor is glad when he can receive anonymized data and is relieved from responsibility for identifiable patient data.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS AIDAVA

Igor hopes that an automatic data curation tool could support him with finding all patients who fulfil specific inclusion and exclusion criteria for research projects or clinical studies. To be useful for him, such a tool must be secure, reliable, easily accessible, convenient to use, and usable for analysis of different data sources. However, as Igor has already experienced AI tools making mistakes, he would not trust this tool 100% and would want to be able to see why the tool found these patients.

Mona Marid, Clinician

Age: 38 * **Education:** Medical Doctor

DIGITAL LITERACY
MEDIUM

MEDICAL LITERACY
HIGH

SKILLS & KNOWLEDGE

- medical knowledge
- analytical thinking
- basic computer user skills
- conscientiousness
- stress resilience
- empathy
- communication

MOTIVATIONS

- difficult & interesting cases
- job is not boring
- opportunity for development
- help patients
- bring in good ideas
- good team

FRUSTRATIONS

- work overload
- no time for learning new things
- shortage of support staff
- lack of mental rewards
- administration & paperwork
- missing data

VALUES & ASPIRATIONS

- desire to develop
- being considerate of others
- self control
- accept different opinions
- good working atmosphere
- respect for colleagues

PERSONALITY AND BEHAVIOUR

Her friends and family would describe Mona as a calm and conscientious person. She is always considerate of others, tries to meet all demands and strives to do all tasks precisely and fast. Mona's favorite hobby is playing the violin. However, since her job is so demanding and she has to do a massive amount of extra hours, she can hardly find any time for her hobby. Mona is not enthusiastic about technological gadgets and getting new technology is not a big thrill for her. She sees electronic devices and software applications as tools that simply should work and support her in completing her tasks. Usually, when she needs to get a new device, she chooses the same brand that she had before so that she does not have to waste time getting acquainted with new technology.

OCCUPATION

Mona works as a medical doctor in the hospital. Looking up patients' health data is an essential part of her daily work since she needs to get an overview of a patient's complete medical history to come up with the right diagnoses and treatment decisions. To access a patient's health records, Mona must authenticate with her ID card, and each access to patients' data is logged by the system. For finding the needed information, she must go through the health record documents of the patient and read a lot of unstructured report texts. Mona is constantly working under time pressure since patients are usually scheduled every 25 minutes and finding information in long medical records is time-consuming. What worries Mona most is the massive work overload in the hospital. She finds it hard to keep pace with the fast changes in her field as she does not have time to learn new things.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS DATA PRIVACY

Mona knows data protection is essential when dealing with people's health data, and according to the hospital's rules, doctors should only look at 'their' patients' records. But sometimes this is a complex issue, e.g. when she accidentally opens the wrong person's records or discusses patient-related matters with a colleague.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS AIDAVA

Mona hopes that an automatic data curation tool could support her in finding the important parts of information in a patient's medical records, and it should extract information from report texts to fill in forms automatically. To be useful for her, such a tool must be fast, reliable, easy to use, and provide a good overview of a patient's medical record. Mona expects the tool to deliver all data. She would trust the tool, if the company says that it works, and would only make some random sample checks every now and then.

3.2.3. Updated data curator personas

Relevant findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study

As described in detail in Section 2.2.1, related aspects from point of view of the expert curators participating in the AIDAVA G1 assessment study were collected in a short questionnaire.

The following table lists those findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study, which are relevant for the elaboration of AIDAVA curator personas, and indicates how these findings are considered in the update of these AIDAVA personas.

Findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study	Respective update of curator personas
Age-range of the expert curators participating in the study: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lower/equal to 40 years 	Already covered by existing curator personas - no update needed
Knowledge and skills necessary for expert curator: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • basic technical skills (basic technological understanding, general knowledge on how to use a smartphone, basic IT skills, basic computer skills) • background knowledge on AIDAVA and related apps (understanding AIDAVA, MIDATA, and Withings apps: their purpose, how they are interconnected, and how to work with them) • clinical data related knowledge, experience reading and interpreting medical data • basic medical knowledge / medical background, entry level knowledge of medical terminology • ability to search and connect reliable medical information and connected codes (such as e.g. SNOMED CT¹⁰, ICD¹¹ etc) • skill to adequately process the medical history and manage to see logical and fundamental mistakes • access to a reliable source of information in case of questions 	Add skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> experience in reading and interpreting medical data; clinical data related knowledge; ability to search reliable medical information and connect codes (e.g. SNOMED CT); ability to see logical and fundamental mistakes;
Personality traits necessary for expert curator: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • good communication, being empathic, enjoying talking to people • friendly, helpful, patient • competent, good attention to detail and follow-through, ability to concentrate on the curated texts, responsibility, focus • enthusiasm, invest much time to understand the curated data 	Already covered by existing curator personas - no update needed

¹⁰ Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) - more information: <https://www.snomed.org>

¹¹ International Classification of Diseases (ICD) - more information: <https://icd.who.int/en>

Findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study	Respective update of curator personas
<p>What they like about the job of an AIDAVA expert curator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● meeting new and different people, being able to talk to people, patient contact and interaction ● being part of a project with potential; the opportunity to contribute to the development of the project; seeing the completion of data entry and the exciting possibilities for the future of medicine and how it could better patient care and prevention ● gain new experience, improve (technical) skills ● organised and well-prepared data; quick tool for data extraction 	<p>Add motivation: seeing the exciting possibilities for the future of medicine and how it could improve patient care and prevention</p>
<p>Motivation for doing the job of an AIDAVA expert curator in the future:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● would be willing to do this job if the system worked well; ● AIDAVA could assist in prevention screening and catching possible medical issues early on for better quality care; ● likes to help patients with personal questions via electronic tool; supporting patients is interesting and full of various challenges; ● likes helping to build reliable information for further use by patients and medical colleagues in daily practice for more accurate clinical decisions; ● making structured, well-organised and easily accessible data a standard that everybody should have; ● reducing the time sacrificed for gathering medical data from different platforms/resources/paper documents/etc.; quick access to the latest status of multimorbid patients with challenging medical history (e.g. oncology, multiple chronic diseases); ● likes helping to develop the system as AIDAVA has potential, and international collaboration offers new experiences and challenges ● helping to implement a worldwide health database; 	<p>Add motivation: structured and easily accessible health data should be standard</p>
<p>Main challenges in the job of an AIDAVA expert curator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● managing multiple responsibilities of AIDAVA in addition to all other daily required tasks that need much attention, is very difficult ● if there will be a lot of (similar/repeating) questions per document, this can potentially cause burnout. ● understanding questions asked by AI and answering these correctly 	<p>Add challenges: understanding questions asked by AI and answer these correctly; having to answer a lot of similar questions may induce a lack of concentration and slips and could potentially end up in burnout;</p>

Findings from AIDAVA G1 assessment study	Respective update of curator personas
<p>Aspects & features an “automatic health data cleaning tool” should have to be practically useful (from point of view of expert curators):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● good data curation by the AI, must work properly and reliably ● user-friendly, easy and simple to handle, also not so many accounts (separate accounts for AIDAVA, MIDATA...) should be needed ● the AI should be able to ask simple and understandable questions; if any questions come up, they should be easy to comprehend and not require a lot of effort and time to answer (otherwise patients will not use it) ● automatic upload of every medical report by all the doctors, hospitals, medical institutions, etc. ● searching tool to search for a keyword ● the tool must be able to recognise mistakes of data registration ● the IPS should be logical, and there should be automatic language translation so that it can be used in other countries too (e.g. in medical emergencies on holidays) ● it should be one source of data for patients and doctors, especially in emergency cases → the tool must provide much data about patients in less time independent of location 	<p>Main aspects already covered by existing curator personas - no update needed</p>

Considering these findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study, the two existing curator personas (developed in Phase 1 of Task 1.2) were updated, whereby the majority of the updates were applied to the data curator persona 2 ('clinical assistant'), as this persona's framework conditions more closely resemble the framework conditions of the expert curators in the AIDAVA G1 assessment study.

Updated foundation for data curator personas

All aspects mentioned in the following personas foundations table are based on the interview results (conducted in Phase 1 of Task 1.2) and updated by the findings from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study in the three AIDAVA sites (collected in Phase 2 of Task 1.2).

	data-curator persona 1 ("researcher")	data-curator persona 2 ("clinical assistant")
age	18-40	18-65
self-description	social person with a lot of friends, likes spending time with colleagues outside of work; likes spending time with friends and family; passionate about new technologies and computers; easy going person, hardworking; serious and friendly person	Likes their work; Interested in people and strives for the well-being of the patients; open minded and curious; enthusiastic medical staff who is annoyed by all the things that distract from the medical work; conscientious, correct, quick/fast, proper, friendly, empathic, precise, innovative, loyal, organized

	data-curator persona 1 ("researcher")	data-curator persona 2 ("clinical assistant")
educational background	Bachelor in medicine and Master in data science, but not a clinical person; educational background in computer and data science;	medical secretary/assistant courses (if no-medical previous education)
digital literacy computer & data literacy	HIGH very good/expert computer user with good computer skills. (self-rating on 0-10 scale: 7; 10; 10)	MEDIUM average self-rated proficiency as computer & smartphone user: 7.25; can handle everyday tasks related to IT, yet there is always room for improvement; uses a computer daily; weak in graphs; enjoys learning new things as this keeps the mind fresh
attitude towards data protection and privacy	believes that data protection and privacy aspects are underestimated and underappreciated within research; necessary for every research project, although it complicates things for certain research goals - you have to take a lot of approvals from different people to acquire data; highly important to deal with data rights and data privacy aspects, because patients need to trust the researchers who deal with their data;	data rights and privacy are very important and also a risk in AIDAVA (e.g. problem if the employer receives those data or insurance companies utilize these data for their purpose - not everybody needs to know what is wrong with patients' health); for research, it is important to have high-quality, correct and complete data – but sometimes data protection & privacy are overstrained and this causes also problems as the related bureaucracy is extremely high; data protection rules are very strict;
attitude towards new technologies	it depends on the device whether to read the manual or not, because it can be a waste of time or it can save a lot of time; likes to read manuals because it saves so much time; - it's like a construction of an IKEA furniture; excited to explore the new functionalities of the new device; there is no problem with giving up the old device because it's taken care of by technology due to the restore to factory settings option;	usually, does not read manuals; consults the manual only when getting stuck or it is a complicated device; always reads the manual - sometimes asking a colleague or expert to help with/show how to use a new device; would look forward to getting a new smartphone, and would gladly use it; feels fine, if a new solution or application makes their work easier; does not get frustrated when having to receive a new device, since there are so many new devices, equipment and systems coming out all the time – however, not all new solutions are helpful;

	data-curator persona 1 ("researcher")	data-curator persona 2 ("clinical assistant")
medical literacy	MEDIUM average self-rated familiarity with medical terms: 7 on a 0-10 scale; some educational background related to medicine and healthcare generally; familiar with medical terms because dealing with medical data; no expert, but has got an idea about medical terms;	HIGH average self-rated familiarity with medical terms: 8 on a 0-10 scale;
job	working as a data engineer; doing a PhD in clinical data science; programming in SQL and MATLAB, and doing some administrative stuff as well; postdoctoral researcher within a clinical data science department; supervision of PhD students within the department and coding; preparing the data for researchers and transforming them into a machine-readable format;	main tasks: patient care and talking to the patients: including patient education, examination, guiding through chemotherapy, aftercare and discussing the reports; additionally: organizational management of the study centre, science and research activities; medical secretary work: filling in data to registries is an added task but main tasks are also related to entering patient data (including myocardial infarction notice, treating physicians' information, patients' data and care records, test results, procedures, medications and billing input); main tasks: organizing the work of the nurses, ordering, work schedules; all personnel related issues; making sure all the input is correct, running tasks include helping the head nurse, help with patient care and cover shifts;

	data-curator persona 1 ("researcher")	data-curator persona 2 ("clinical assistant")
important skills for the job	<p>programming/coding skills and semantic web technologies that transform data into machinery that will format according to a specific set of principles called FAIRdata principles; development of applications; statistical analysis;</p> <p>you have to be precise and extremely careful with the medical data you are using and you have to clean them in a specific way in order to be usable;</p> <p>communication skills with people in order to understand and execute tasks and needs of a specific project; you should also be open minded; patience is one of the important traits a clinical data scientist should have;</p> <p>project management skills; dealing with a half dozen international and national research projects;</p>	<p>most important for doing the job well: you have to like this job and this work - the skills you need to do this job are acquired over time; you should be able to think yourself, work independently and stay calm;</p> <p>prerequisite to working here is a general knowledge of what goes on in our (medical) field, administrative skills, basic medical knowledge, experience reading and interpreting medical data, clinical data knowledge, skill to adequately process medical history and manage to see logical and fundamental mistakes;</p> <p>ability to search and connect reliable medical information (SNOMED code etc.);</p> <p>background knowledge on AIDAVA, MIDATA and Withings: their purpose, how they are interconnected and how to work with them;</p> <p>language skills (including local language + largest ethnic minorities, tourists' languages and English, sometimes medical Latin);</p> <p>skills needed in this job: proper education, basic computer/IT skills, administrative skills, and also medical skills as you need to take shifts in care of patients;</p> <p>traits needed: patience, dealing with emotions (your own and others), there are a lot of people and (sometimes difficult) personalities around you – in general you need to have a pretty thick skin to do this job;</p> <p>conscientiousness, precise, good attention to detail and follow-through; ability to concentrate on the curated texts, responsibility, focus; have a wide understanding of many things, friendly and helpful, empathic, multitasking;</p>

	data-curator persona 1 ("researcher")	data-curator persona 2 ("clinical assistant")
I like most in job	<p>communication with colleagues in the office and out of the office as well, enjoy collaborating with people and have face to face contact with them; working together on different projects; independence by working from wherever and whenever you want; improve patient's lives and treatments; love helping people to make decisions based on data; implementation of new technology within medicine; love the application of programming in healthcare; application of new technology (new era of artificial intelligence) in healthcare and therefore the ability to improve patients' lives;</p>	<p>communication/working with colleagues, improve patients' lives; combination of the fact that the work is professionally demanding and interesting on the one hand, and on the other hand you can also support the patients over a longer period; the job itself is interesting, there is not a lot of routine; love working with patients because it is practical work; enjoy having nice colleagues, the field of work, teamwork, fast paced work and decisions, variation of administrative and medical tasks; enjoy working /communicating with colleagues and if you get your job done and people are pleased with you; the working room is nice and warm, and the equipment (to work with) is ok;</p>
challenge in job	<p>there is not enough legal standardised framework to use patients' data within our organization - due to that dealing with laws, lawyers and different data privacy officers to acquire data is extremely difficult; problems with the extraction of medical data from hospital are the time consuming part and it's really stressful; don't really like debugging in coding; hate time pressure and deadlines; hate politics in my world because you require approvals; need to build personal or other interests from a company and this is really annoying to me; collaborating with people because they usually have different time schedules and can be difficult personality; lots of meetings during my daily work; commuting to work - prefer working from home;</p>	<p>time pressure/not enough time to finish tasks; time factor: sometimes feeling that you can't finish your work; increasing bureaucracy in every respect, technical solutions are urgently needed to support these bureaucracy tasks; bureaucracy / dealing with laws&politics; managing responsibilities of AIDAVA in addition to all other daily required tasks that need much attention, is very difficult; patients have to wait so long to be examined, there are no more patient beds, you don't know where to admit patients; health insurance checks for the patients - there used to be a phone number you could call to check but that does not exist anymore; often the system info is not correct; new programs you need to use and learn that appear quite often; having to answer a lot of similar questions may induce a lack of concentration and slips and could potentially end up in burnout; main challenge is communication with people; new devices and programs are usually not an issue;</p>

	data-curator persona 1 ("researcher")	data-curator persona 2 ("clinical assistant")
current approach for health data curation	<p>using and retrieving patients' health data to implement prediction modelling within the healthcare domain and specifically radiotherapy; using EHR data that are collected within the different data storage systems of the hospitals; mainly uses SPARQL queries to retrieve the data from the hospital systems; uses some statistical analysis tools like R Studio to clean and get the data ready for research; main task is developing prediction models based on deep learning techniques; uses patient data to implement algorithms that delineate medical images using deep learning techniques; mainly deals with CT and MRI images and receives these images in DICOM format from the EHR systems of hospitals; stores data in SQL Server; retrieves patients' health data to implement artificial intelligence algorithms for prediction modelling; transforms this data into a machinery that will format using fair data principles and semantic web technologies;</p>	<p>it is a significant amount of labour to clean data; collecting data from a patient to create a (treatment) plan actually includes everything: data entry, curation, and use - currently all of that is done manually; medical findings have to be collected from everywhere: from the national electronic health records, from the evaluating institute, sometimes the patients bring reports from other physicians, sometimes we get a CD, sometimes the medical information is in another language and we need translation - it is always different and very diverse; some data are put into the hospital system but some are not - if data are missing, sometimes they ask the patient or check the ambulance card and notes; gets the data both from the information system and from the national system;</p>
current challenges in data curation	<p>main challenges are missing data and data that does not make sense; there are different formats that the data are given to me – it is a challenge to clean the data and have a standardised way of format; keeping track of several projects is a challenge when you are not good at project management;</p>	<p>sometimes the information does not match and then you have to look more closely; sometimes, you can only rely on the image data; doctors are urgently calling for measures to reduce workload, so that patients do not all come to us for aftercare, but the general practitioners and technology should take over; main challenges is that they cannot access all needed data and some of the data is missing; it is extra work to look for and enter data to registries;</p>

<p>attitude towards automatic health data cleaning</p>	<p>the system has to be secure because this tool will deal with patient data, so it's extremely significant to have a security framework within this system; the system has to be user friendly so that users do not have to spend a lot of time to find all the different aspects of this system; the system has to be collectively owned - it has to be public, open to the people who are interested in curation and collection of data of patients; this system has to be a server-based system and this system should be something like a cloud-based system; it has to be user friendly: it has to be machine readable using fair data principles and API; The ideal system includes an automation of errors detection that may exist in a data set; privacy-preserving data exchange or data modelling exchange within the different participants is also important; recommendation is really important to this tool; standard terminologies have to be used in order to achieve a standardisation framework of the data sets and the data that are used within this tool; the ideal data curation and publishing machine would include standardised terminologies and extract common entities from it;</p>	<p>the system must be user friendly, self-explanatory and secure so that data is protected; it must deliver correct results and should have error detection; questions asked by the AI must be easy to understand so that the patient/curator can answer these correctly; the system should be able to filter the right information for the specific user; we need a simplification of communication and fewer patient-hospital contacts: AIDAVA should be less work and not more! laboratory checks should be automatically uploaded to the system, including a warning e.g. if leukocytes are below the normal value; the system should ask the patient correctly everything that is needed, and tell the patient what to do when this or that arises; general information about the patient (phone number, home address, contact info) should be automatically added from the system; the system should collect all needed data from different places: diagnosis, test results, procedure information; it would also be good to know whether patients have allergies, smoke or not (and how old is this information – maybe they quit smoking), what home treatment and what medications; should also include data that are currently only on paper; speech to text function would also be helpful; it would be great if there could be a machine that collects all necessary data and puts it in a register/form - currently, there are so many clicks and ticks in the information system, and you have to make sure you don't forget anything - it's those clicks that made our work very busy today; AIDAVA should keep track so that registry fields that have already been checked don't have to be checked again; it should point out if a field is blank and ask why it is blank; it should be possible to put a mark on the field so that the information doesn't change again; AIDAVA provides exciting possibilities for the future of medicine and how it could better patient care and prevention;</p>
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Updated visualisations of the data curator personas

Helga Johanson, Clinical assistant

Age: 50* Education: clinical assistant, nurse

DIGITAL LITERACY

MEDIUM

MEDICAL LITERACY

HIGH

SKILLS & KNOWLEDGE

- solution orientated
- language skills
- administrative skills
- communication
- accuracy
- computer skills
- medical knowledge

MOTIVATIONS

- improve patient's lives
- nice colleagues
- good working conditions
- independence
- continuous development
- interesting job

FRUSTRATIONS

- time pressure
- information system errors
- people's different time schedules
- increasing bureaucracy
- missing data

VALUES & ASPIRATIONS

- professionally demanding
- modern equipment
- good working atmosphere
- new technology

PERSONALITY AND BEHAVIOUR

Helga is interested in people and strives for the well-being of patients. She is open-minded and curious. Colleagues say that Helga is a friendly, empathetic person and a good communicator. She is always conscientious, and has a good attention to detail. Helga is hardworking and organized and completes her tasks fast. She thinks that in her work with registries' data it is of utmost importance to work precisely and take care that everything is correct. In data curation, Helga finds it difficult to stay focused and concentrated when she has to answer a huge amount of similar questions and she fears that this may result in slips and mistakes. The main challenges at her work are the amount of new programs she needs to learn to use and dealing with relationships between people with various personalities. If Helga gets a new device it is not difficult for her to start using it. She usually consults the manual first, and if that does not help, she asks for advice from a specialist.

OCCUPATION

Helga has been working in the medical field for over 20 years. Her main tasks are patient care, including patient education, guiding the treatment process and discussing reports. Entering data into registries is an additional task for Helga, but her main tasks are also related to entering patient data into the hospital's information system. Every morning, she goes through all information system areas which she is responsible for and makes sure that all entries are correct. Over the years Helga has got experience in reading and interpreting medical data and acquired a lot of knowledge related to clinical data. She knows where to find reliable medical information and how to identify connected medical codes. These skills are essential for her work in data curation as they help to discover logical and fundamental mistakes. Helga likes her job because it is not boring. But she finds it annoying when the information systems do not work properly, or when she has to enter the same information over and over again.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS DATA PRIVACY

Helga feels that it is beneficial for science and patient care to gather all health data in one place, but it is risky if an employer or insurance company uses these data for their own purpose. Data privacy is important. Thus, access to patient data must be restricted, and tools handling patient data must be secure.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS AIDAVA

Helga believes AIDAVA will bring exciting possibilities for future improvement in prevention and patient care. Structured, easily accessible health data should be standard for all. Helga thinks AIDAVA should be simple and user-friendly. The questions asked by the AI must be easy to understand so that she is able to answer correctly. To support her work, information about the patient should be added to AIDAVA from different sources automatically. AIDAVA should detect errors that may exist in data sets. It should also provide an alert system if health indicators are abnormal.

Jonas Thompson, Researcher

Age: 33* Education: PhD clinical data science

DIGITAL LITERACY

HIGH

MEDICAL LITERACY

MEDIUM

SKILLS & KNOWLEDGE

- Programming/coding
- Good communicator
- Precise
- Patience
- Open-minded
- Semantic web technologies
- Project management

MOTIVATIONS

- Ability to improve patient lives/treatments
- independence in tasks
- collaboration
- Enjoy the application of technology in healthcare

FRUSTRATIONS

- Legal paperwork
- Commuting
- Debugging
- work with non-collaborative and busy people
- Non-standardized data
- Time pressure and deadlines
- Missing data

VALUES & ASPIRATIONS

- Being the boss of your own time
- Values face to face interactions
- Enjoys helping people
- passion for research

PERSONALITY AND BEHAVIOUR

People describe Jonas as social, tech-savvy and hard-working person. In his spare time Jonas loves to spend time with his colleagues, family and friends. He loves learning new things. Assembling IKEA furniture or adapting to new technologies is no problem for him. Currently, when Jonas is not programming or coding, he is helping to supervise PhD students. He is always happy to help out in administrative tasks if needed. He really enjoys helping people to make decisions based on data. When he gets a new device, he is excited to explore all the new possibilities and does not worry about data getting lost when changing smartphones. He has no problems navigating new devices without a manual but depending on the device reading the manual first can save a lot of time.

OCCUPATION

Jonas works in research projects in the medical data field and supervises PhD students. As a data engineer and researcher at a medical university Jonas's main tasks are programming, coding and development. A big part of his work is to transform and clean the data into machine readable or standardized form. Jonas really hates all the time consuming legal and ethical paperwork that comes with processing medical data. It substantially slows down the work process. Jonas likes it very much to be the boss of his own time and have the ability to work from home as well. He also enjoys to apply his abilities in programming to healthcare and see it used to improve patient lives or treatment.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS DATA PRIVACY

Jonas believes that data protection and privacy issues are underestimated and underappreciated within research - especially in healthcare. Privacy aspects are very necessary in every research although it sometimes complicates things for certain research goals since it is so time consuming to get permissions.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS AIDAVA

One of the most important factors for Jonas is that this tool is secure since it deals with patient data. Also it needs to be user friendly to save time for all users. Jonas finds it important for AIDAVA to be collectively owned - it has to be a public server based (cloud) system and available to all who are interested in data collection and curation. The ideal system should in addition to automation have error detection. It should use standardized frameworks of the data sets and extract common entities from it.

3.2.4. Updated third-party app developer personas

No major updates of the third-party app developer personas were needed in Phase 2 of Task 1.2, as the AIDAVA G1 assessment study brought about no new insights with respect to this user group. Only minor updates of the scales for digital and medical literacy of these personas were made, so that the description of these personas is consistent with the updated personas for the other user groups of AIDAVA.

Updated foundation for 3rd party app developer personas

All aspects mentioned in the following personas foundations table are based on the results of the interviews conducted in Phase 1 of Task 1.2.

	app developer persona 1 user persona ("software developer")	app developer persona 2 customer persona ("manager")
education	study of medical informatics and communication science	study of psychology / molecular biology / computer science;
career	worked for several years in hospital administration and health-related communication;	co-founder and board member of digital health / software development company; worked for 20 years as CTO in software industry; work profile evolved from doing lots of programming in earlier days to now having mainly organisational and management tasks; working in health care system policy consulting for 20 years;
current job	developing software for health-related apps	CTO, leading and coordinating the developer teams of a digital health company - responsible for project management and timelines; board member of digital health / software development company;
main motivation in job	likes logical and structured thinking; enjoys solving problems and debugging - i.e. finding solutions for stuff that does not work;	
main frustration / challenge in job	in another project they do not have a real test environment and the partner's implementation is not available for testing 24/7	The highest hurdle is the reimbursement system: even if you have evidence for the functioning of a health IT solution, it's not clear who pays for a health IT solution.
digital literacy	HIGH	HIGH very high data literacy (consultant for government in data privacy/protection issues; expert in state-of-the-art software technology)

	app developer persona 1 user persona ("software developer")	app developer persona 2 customer persona ("manager")
medical literacy	LOW	MEDIUM familiarity with medical terms is high (consultant for government and co-lead of health-related national research program; expert in HL7-FHIR - currently developing a connection with national health terminology server)
attitude towards health-data privacy	data protection in health-related field is extremely important, as you cannot make it undone when data is leaked; health-data should be accessible in a way that patients can understand, and the patients should be able to decide with whom they want to share their data; (current problem: legally the data owners are the patients, but practically the real owners are medical doctors)	health data privacy is very important - when you want to enter DIGA or CE, you have to have all the data privacy and data protection aspects covered. It's pretty complicated. (We follow the required privacy and security guidelines from the ministry of health (like ISO 27001 and NEN 7510 certification and a yearly penetration test on the software done by an external party). We enter into an era of 2nd use of health data and need to be transparent with what we do with the data. You must make sure that a patient understands but not overestimates the implication of sharing data; emphasizing the giant value for society in having this kind of data that allows to build decision support systems, that will ultimately benefit all patients;
expectations towards AIDAVA	important that API is well documented; need a test environment that's available 24/7; it must be transparent what can be expected from the tool; ideally, if I have to go to the hospital I want the doctor to see a report of two pages about my health that contains everything relevant and correct;	In an AIDAVA setting, our company could put data in. We don't see our platform as a standalone solution and integrate into other platforms depending on the use case. The ideas in AIDAVA are something where we as a company want to go - eager to learn about possibilities of AI, specifically also in PROM tools. Our company's use case: focus on the collection of health information for the individual - medical data and individual lifestyle (e.g. activity and other lifestyle activities like alcohol and tobacco use, personalized nutrition) in collaboration with research and pharma institutes.

	app developer persona 1 user persona ("software developer")	app developer persona 2 customer persona ("manager")
attitude towards automatic health-data curation and publishing		<p>Good data curation in healthcare is important. For that, you need a top down approach from the ministry of health (by law healthcare providers need to deliver the medical data in a FHIR format), and when this works we have a solution for structured data (not yet for unstructured) - for an ideal world it will take several years.</p> <p>Key issue: lots of the data in clinical records is plain unstructured text - it would make sense feeding textual data to AIDAVA and reading back structured, interpreted data we can use in visualisation;</p> <p>Key advantage of AIDAVA: meaningful structured data from unstructured data; you can compare it to a population and use it for a decision support system.</p> <p>Another valuable use case: Let's say you have three hospitals recording the same data in a structured way, but they do it in different structures because there is no overarching agreement on what the exact structure should be. If AIDAVA would be able to get from all these hospitals these data fields and also some form of metadata on what those fields mean in the context of that hospital, then translating the values from each of these hospitals into a knowledge graph compatible with all of these representations would be very valuable;</p>
attitudes towards AI	<p>It must be transparent when data are aggregated where the data came from and which sources are used;</p> <p>Many people are sceptical about whether AI can be as good as humans in data curation - the possibility to see what exactly the system did to generate the curated data is essential for trustworthiness;</p>	<p>Key problem in AI and machine learning: how to verify the validity of the output of the algorithm? In a (anonymized) registry there's no way to ever know whether the automatically curated data was correct. You'll always need, in the medical context, having a person verify the output. If you replace an unstructured piece of data with a structured piece of data, as a physician you can't use that structured data to base your decision on.</p> <p>AI must improve efficiency and quality of care. (You cannot motivate clinical staff to do more work)</p>

Visualisations of the app developer personas

Didi Drdlik, Software Developer

Age: 37 * **Education:** Study of Medical Informatics

DIGITAL LITERACY
HIGH

MEDICAL LITERACY
LOW

SKILLS & KNOWLEDGE

- programming
- data understanding
- persistence
- creativity
- logical thinking
- structured working

MOTIVATIONS

- solving interesting problems
- job is not boring
- completing tasks
- finding bugs and solutions

FRUSTRATIONS

- unclear specifications
- unrealistic deadlines
- missing documentation in third party software
- insufficient test environment

VALUES & ASPIRATIONS

- good work/life balance
- rejoice in his work
- self-determined working hours and workflow

PERSONALITY AND BEHAVIOUR

His friends and family would describe Didi as an easygoing and optimistic person. Didi has been interested in technical gadgets since his childhood. His friends frequently ask for his advice with respect to computers, smart watches or mobile phones since Didi is always well-informed about new technologies and knows the state-of-the-art products. In his leisure time, Didi likes playing computer games or going out with his friends to play a round of billiards.

OCCUPATION

After finishing his university studies in medical informatics, Didi worked for some years in the hospital administration and health-related communication sector before he started his current job as a software developer in a digital health company. As part of a team of eight software developers, Didi is responsible for the maintenance and implementation of new features in the company's health-related apps. Tasks and issues are distributed according to a plan among the developers in the team. Most of the time, the software developers work on the assigned tasks on their own. However, they are in close contact with each other, and each day a short meeting with the teammates is scheduled. Didi aims to fulfil the tasks assigned to him always on time and in good quality.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS DATA PRIVACY

Didi thinks that data protection in the health sector is extremely important as you cannot make it undone when health data is leaked. He believes that health data should be accessible in a way patients can understand, and the patients should be empowered to decide with whom they want to share their data.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS AIDAVA

When it comes to cooperation with AIDAVA, as a software developer Didi would want to know in detail what he can expect from that tool. He would hope that the API is well documented and a test environment is available 24/7. Regarding AI-based data curation, Didi finds it extremely important for trustworthiness to have the possibility to see what exactly the system did to generate the curated data and which sources are used.

Alec Aarn, Chief Technical Officer

Age: 61 * **Education:** Study of Molecular Biology

DIGITAL LITERACY
HIGH

MEDICAL LITERACY
MEDIUM

SKILLS & KNOWLEDGE

- management
- data understanding
- coordination
- networking
- communication
- policy consulting
- business sense

MOTIVATIONS

- fruitful cooperation
- staying on the ball
- development of the company
- business opportunity

FRUSTRATIONS

- reimbursement system in healthcare
- finance issues
- bureaucracy
- uncooperative people

VALUES & ASPIRATIONS

- value for society
- rejoice in his work
- collaboration
- leadership

PERSONALITY AND BEHAVIOUR

His friends and family would describe Alec as a correct, communicative, solution-oriented and always forward-looking person with a great sense of humour. Alec loves to discuss about politics and society and is also very interested in technological trends and innovations. Alec thinks that it is very important to never rest on one's oars but always keep learning. Thus, he often spends after-work hours reading newspapers and technical journals to keep up with societal as well as technological developments.

OCCUPATION

Alec is a co-founder and board member of a digital health company, which is developing software solutions and applications focusing on the collection of health information for the individual. As CTO of the company, Alec is leading and coordinating the developer teams and has mainly got organizational and management tasks. In addition, Alec has been working in healthcare system policy consulting for over 20 years. He is a consultant for the government in health-data issues and is actively involved with health-related national research programs. According to Alec, currently, the biggest challenge for IT companies in the healthcare sector is the reimbursement system, as it is not clear who pays for a health IT solution.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS DATA PRIVACY

Alec believes that data privacy is very important in the health sector and the company needs to strictly follow the respective privacy & security guidelines from the national ministry. However, Alec thinks for societal benefits it is also essential to ensure that patients understand but do not overestimate the implications of sharing data.

ATTITUDES TOWARDS AIDAVA

Alec knows that having good data curation in healthcare is important as lots of the data in clinical records are plain unstructured text. Thus, Alec is eager to learn about the possibilities of AI and the AIDAVA system, as the ideas in AIDAVA fit with where the company wants to go. However, as Alec knows that verifying the output of a machine learning algorithm is still the key problem in AI, he believes that in a medical context, you will still need to have a person verifying the automatically curated data.

3.3 User profiles

A user profile is a collection of information and settings associated with an individual user within a system, application, or online platform. It represents a unique identity for a user and typically includes personal attributes (e.g. user's name, age, gender...), and preference-related attributes, such as for example language, time zone, theme, notification preferences, or privacy settings.

User profiles serve several purposes, including personalization, customization, and user management. They allow users to maintain their unique identity, tailor their experience, and access personalised content or features within the system. User profiles also enable system administrators and operators to manage user accounts, track user behaviour, and provide targeted services or recommendations.

In generation G2 of the AIDAVA prototype, the user profiles of the patients and expert curators will also include attributes derived from the analysis of the personas that are relevant to customise the human-computer interaction (HCI). Approaches to adapt human-computer interaction in AIDAVA to the skills of the user are developed in Task 5.3 of the AIDAVA project. Specifically, in generation G2 of the AIDAVA prototype, the level of technical complexity of the information provided in the explainability part of the human-computer interaction will be adapted to the digital literacy level of a patient or expert curator, and the medical literacy of the patient will be used in the human-in-the-loop (HITL) part of the human-computer interaction to decide if a question that occurs in the curation workflow can be sent to the patient or should be sent to the expert curator.

All attributes related to the user profiles will be stored in a dedicated data store ("User Directory"), as specified in the Deliverable 2.3 - Solution Design.

4 Summary and next steps

In Phase 2 of Task 1.2 of the AIDAVA project, the AIDAVA personas were successfully updated based on the findings and insights from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study, and the citizens' survey was re-run in order to gain insights from a broader group of respondents regarding citizens' attitudes towards sharing their health data, using an automatic health data curation tool, and the main functionalities they would expect from such a tool.

Update of the AIDAVA personas according to the insights gained from the AIDAVA G1 assessment study resulted in nine personas: 3 patient personas (one more than described in D1.2), 2 data user personas, 2 data curator personas and 2 third-party app developer personas. Thereby, major updates were applied to the patient and curator personas, and only minor updates were needed for data user and third-party app developer personas. The major updates of the patient personas were related to usage of a smartphone for working with AIDAVA as well as the patients' approaches for uploading documents to AIDAVA through the Health Data Intermediary (HDI) and the patients' strategies for overcoming problems when using AIDAVA. Major updates of the data curator personas were related to their skills, motivation and challenges with respect to the job of an AIDAVA data curator. The minor adjustments for data user and third-party app developer personas were mainly related to wording regarding medical and digital literacy to make these consistent across all personas.

For each of the nine personas, an updated foundation document was formulated and an updated visualisation in form of a personas canvas was elaborated.

From the citizens' survey (Phase 1: 250 participants, Phase 2: 131 participants) we could conclude that nearly all (Phase 1: 91%, Phase 2: >89%) of the survey respondents are interested in keeping their medical dossier in a central place. In addition, the majority (Phase 1: 78%, Phase 2: 85%) of the survey respondents would be willing to contribute to increasing the quality of their medical dossier. The main reason for doing so is to ensure the treating physicians have access to the appropriate information, particularly in emergency situations.

Noticeable in the context of AIDAVA is that only a bit more than half of the survey respondents (Phase 1: 54%, Phase 2: 59%) would - currently - be interested in using a digital 'data cleaning' tool to support them. Interestingly, this number increases substantially (Phase 1: 81%, Phase 2: 71%) for the survey respondents with an active medical dossier. This seems to demonstrate that, when there is no real need, people put more consideration to the risks than to the benefits. Thus, this finding supports the need to ensure high security and reliability of the system, together with user training covering both data literacy as well as the risk and benefits of a system like AIDAVA.

This is also supported by the interviews and the resulting personas, where we found that especially people who are not so tech-savvy are rather anxious regarding online insecurity and worried about threats of data leaks, viruses, and hackers. These people are also rather reluctant to share their medical data with anybody else but their treating medical staff. It is important to take these findings into account when developing training materials and user guidance. For example, it must be taken care that security aspects of the AIDAVA system are not only described in technical detail to cater for the needs of a system administrator, but are also well explained in layman language addressing the concerns of (not so tech-savvy) users.

This deliverable and the associated material and results created during Task 1.2. will support a user-centred development of the AIDAVA “AI-based data curation & publishing assistant”. The personas will support the project partners to share the same understanding of the different user roles in AIDAVA. Furthermore, the personas also help in the development of the generation G2 of AIDAVA to empathise with the different user groups so that developers can take decisions with the users in mind. This should lead to more user-centric decisions. In this sense, the personas complement the business requirements specified in Task 1.3 of the AIDAVA project.

Attributes derived from main characteristics of the personas, such as digital and medical literacy, will be included in the AIDAVA user profiles for patients and expert curators, and will be used in Task 5.3 to adapt the human-computer interaction to the users’ skills.

The next steps to ensure that the material and results created during Task 1.2 will be used effectively for user-centred development of the AIDAVA “AI-based data curation & publishing assistant” include:

- **Persona communication:** We will share the updated personas (canvas and foundation documents) with the project partners and development teams and make sure everyone understands the personas and their characteristics relevant in shaping the generation G2 of the AIDAVA prototype.
- **Requirements prioritisation:** When updating the requirements for generation G2 of the AIDAVA prototype in Task 1.3, we will prioritize addressing the main points, goals, and preferences of personas representing the target users of the AIDAVA prototype. This will ensure the most essential features and functionalities are developed first.
- **Customised human-AI interaction:** In Task 5.3 we consider the attributes digital and medical literacy derived from the personas to ensure that human interaction and explanation components of the AIDAVA prototype are developed according to the needs of the target groups.

5 References

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